

BASTIONE

case study

**ARTISTS
BEYOND
THE MARKET.
THE CASE OF
INDEPENDENT
ART SPACES
AND THEIR
ROLE IN
CONTEMPORARY
SOCIETY**

A research on young contemporary art realities in Turin

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***Artists beyond the market.
The case of independent art spaces
and their role in contemporary society***

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Summary

A market system that raises the monetary value of the artwork to the single indicator of the success of an individual artistic practice (Zorloni, 2016; Isales, 2016) has the consequence of degrading the fundamental concept of art and, hence, the position of the artist. In fact, a study of market dynamics discloses a commercial view of the work of art that finally hides its semantic and symbolic value (Santagata, 1998; Throsby, 1999). This method explains a creative process whereby the artist answers the opinions of curators, art dealers, and critics. Within the framework of the art market, information surplus rather than information shortage poses the primary challenge. This is unlike the dynamics of information asymmetries seen in other sectors (Trimarchi, 2004; Zorloni, 2013; Beckert and Rossel, 2013). Consequently, the work of art becomes a mere utilitarian instrument limited by the restrictions of a small, controlled environment, under the authority of a chosen group of gatekeepers. Such a system makes the artist forsake experimentation in order to create a network that might improve the work and influence its market value (Frey and Pommerehne, 1989; Sacco, 2005).

The state of the art of economic and humanistic studies of the art market, as well as the needs expressed by contemporary artists, the public and the non-public, clearly show the urgency of overcoming an established system that is now an obstacle to the total artistic and cultural dissemination of the work. Indeed, there is a large part of contemporary artistic production that bypasses the barriers of the market, basing its practices on the production of artistic (Sharon, 1979), personal (Wright, 2024) and social (Grodach, 2010) value. This artistic production is conventionally defined as independent.

These premises lead to the need to develop research that asks how independent art spaces reshape the boundaries between the market, the public sector, and the civil sphere in contemporary cultural production. The aim of the study is therefore to examine the economic and organisational characteristics, the institutional profiles and the social impact of independent art spaces.

The research is developed through three sub-questions, which help to answer the main research question: How do independent art spaces reshape the boundaries between the market, the public sector, and the civil sphere in contemporary cultural production? The first sub-question concerns the ways in which these spaces challenge the dynamics, formats and definitions dictated by the market, and asks: In what ways do independent art spaces organize cultural production through collective use, co-creation, and situated governance? Economic and humanistic studies on these spaces defines them as independent, as an expression of reaction to the exhibition and commercial dynamics imposed by the market. However, this conception has the risk of neglecting the characteristics of these practices, which in fact prove to be independent of the market. So what is the context that gives rise to individual independent practices, and how does it influence their practices and organisation? And how and to what extent does this affect the conventional logic of the market?

In studies that look at informal art spaces from the perspective of the urban dimension and their relationship to the city, attention to the context that regulates and determines the emergence and development of independent art practices plays a greater role. These studies complement the previous ones and help to formulate the second sub-question: How do these practices generate and negotiate value(s) that escape conventional economic or policy-driven evaluative frameworks? A question that points research towards the observation of urban dynamics, but which does not overlook the fact that these practices always remain linked to artistic, before social, experimentation.

The third sub-question relates to institutions and the context: What contextual conditions (urban, social, political) enable or constrain these alternative modes of cultural production? The definition of an independent space, derived from art history and cultural economic studies, raises some questions about the meaning that the spaces themselves give to the concept of independence. It is an important concept because it raises ideological questions (artistic independence vs. autonomy), but also economic ones (independence from the commercial logic of the market and therefore from public funding?).

Given that the literature review and the questions it raises obviously touch on areas that go beyond the mere commercial value of the artwork, the adoption of a specific analytical framework to guide the empirical investigation, capable of taking into account all values, proves indispensable. After a review of the economic and humanities studies from which the aforementioned issues emerged, and a consequent review of the value associated with cultural property, the framework of the value-based approach is built (Klamer, 2016). This introduces the need to recognise the existence of multiple factors for the evaluation and valorisation of the creative product. The framework, based on the recognition of five value spheres (market, governance, cultural, social, *oikos*), guided the construction of the research. Then, the methodology applied to a single case study is outlined and the context related to the art market and urban regeneration processes is presented. Finally, the findings are presented, providing the basis for the concluding discussion.

The analysis was conducted through the observation of the practices of the Collettivo Bastione, a group of artists active in an independent space in the city of Turin. Today, their practice takes place at Villa Rey, a 17th-century building located on the hills of Turin, granted by the Municipality of Turin to the Associazione Villa dell'Arte, which carried out the restorations and collaborates with Associazione

Bastione to promote events related to art, music, and performance. Bastione is a research space that hosts and promotes young contemporary artistic realities; it is a meeting place and an exchange between various personalities with the aim of enhancing the cultural offerings in the city of Turin. It was born as an artistic collective in 2017 within the spaces of the Bastione San Maurizio, from which it takes its name. The Bastione's practice emerged during an occupation of one of the buildings that make up the Cavallerizza Reale, a Garittone from 1670, located in the historic center of Turin and still in partial abandonment.

It is in this dimension of horizontality and verticality, settlement and movement, recycling and transformation that the collective's experience can be placed. The care and redevelopment work carried out at the historic Bastione San Maurizio building immediately highlighted the spirit of the artists, driven by the need to regenerate a place that was a physical representation of a shared need. The occupation was a declaration of affirmation, a desire to make a self-determined mark that would not dissolve into silence. The state of abandonment and precariousness of the place, perceived as a reflection of a sentiment, was for the artists a stimulus for storytelling and connecting places and people, a possibility to change the very perspective of creating art. The identification with Bastione San Maurizio led the collective to a methodology that distances itself from authorial independence and from exhibition within the structured and hierarchical art system. By opening up to a plurality of languages, the creative process became the lifeblood of a sharing that activated the space in all its forms.

Therefore, Associazione Bastione is, on the one hand, 15 visual artists who met at the Accademia Albertina and struggled with their first attempts to enter the art market. On the other, an artistic practice that began as an informal practice in a space occupied by visual artists, performers, theatre people and musicians. In addition to presenting multiple artistic projects, some of the artists in the collective present their thesis projects within the occupied walls—experiences and activities

that they will be forced to interrupt after the eviction from the Cavallerizza Reale. It is precisely in the mnemonic fabric that the experience of Bastione San Maurizio is now preserved, whose activity, now concluded, tries to be reborn in other places. After the eviction, in 2020, the collective formulated its statute with the desire to carry the project forward. Since 2019, the year of the eviction, the members of Bastione have continued their practice without a space, while in the meantime, they have formed an association.

From 2019, the year of the eviction from Cavallerizza, the young people of Bastione continued their practice without a space. In the meantime, they formed an association until 2020, when the local authorities granted them a concession for some spaces in Villa Rey. Here, after an initial period of settling in, their artistic practice became more mature and aware. Their previous practice, which laid the foundations for their current one, was characterised by a transitory approach, due to the state of occupation and the difficulty of dialogue with institutions. In Villa Rey, on the other hand, it is a formal practice in its first stage, and therefore in need of planning, strategy and organisation.

The empirical research conducted in 2024 provided answers to the research questions and clarified the cause and effect relationships between the market, urban structures and the concept of independence. In terms of the relationship with the market, Bastion's practice began as a necessary departure from the academy. It was there that the artists had their first contact with the dynamics of the market: a contact that created in them a distance and a fear of this system. But it was the lack of space and relationships that eventually caused the disconnection from the academy and then from the system itself. In this respect, the Cavallerizza and the Bastione San Maurizio proved to be the most suitable contexts for artistic experimentation in an abandoned space and in contact with different disciplines. A context in which the freedom offered by the context and the informality of the relationships have replaced the dynamics of the market.

This is where relating to space and relating to the urban community comes in. Bastione develops an artistic practice centred on the care of spaces, promoting processes of redevelopment of abandoned public spaces through artistic architectural restoration (an internationally recognised and consolidated practice that finds its greatest expression in examples such as Inhotim in Brazil). The care of spaces becomes a fundamental premise for the creation of a community formed around the spaces where Bastione realises its artistic projects. These events bring together the visual, performing and musical arts, and inaugurate an artistic practice that blurs the conventional concepts of artistic creation (individual, in a studio) and fruition (the format of an exhibition in a museum).

The picture is completed by Bastione's concept of his practice at Bastione San Maurizio before and at Villa Rey today. For them, the definition of independence is entirely determined by the logic of the market. In the common sense, the concept of independence does not define a practice embedded in a particular context, but rather an ideological detachment from the market. Instead, each informal art practice is unique precisely because it is the context that determines its forms and directions. Speaking of autonomy becomes more useful, a concept capable of defining the limits of artistic activity free of impositions.

The results of the analysis lead to the formulation of general conclusions that contribute to the knowledge and interpretation of the values underlying the organisation of informal and autonomous practices. Cultural policy implications for artistic practices are presented in the final part of the thesis. This is based on the need for:

- A network of infrastructures (spaces, technologies, connections);

- It is based on four key principles: the transversality and dynamism of roles, openness to confrontation, internal and external collaboration.
- Artistic autonomy and the search for sustainable ways to make it last;
- Engage in dialogue with the local administration and banking foundations to narrate their own practice, rather than allowing calls for proposals and bureaucracy to channel it into categories that do not fit;
- Realization of societal impact through activation of urban regeneration and community development

Although the research findings are specific to the context of Associazione Bastione, they contribute to a more general understanding of informal artistic practices and how they relate to the market, urban dynamics and institutions. It seeks to promote a perspective in which independent practices should no longer be analyzed as anomalies. Rather as practical examples of overcoming conventional models towards a paradigm yet to be defined where artists act as part of civil society.

The aim of this research was to give a voice to Bastion's practice and, above all, their vision. As with any work of individual research, there is a personal motivation behind it. With this dissertation I hope to contribute to a restoration of the value of art as an existential practice, precisely because it is a transcendental expression of being and an incisive response to the urgency of self-representation.

Sintesi

Un sistema di mercato in cui il valore monetario dell'opera d'arte è elevato a unico criterio per decretare il successo di una pratica artistica individuale (Zorloni, 2016; Isales, 2016) determina l'atrofia dell'arte e, con essa, dell'artista. L'analisi delle dinamiche di mercato restituisce, infatti, una concezione commerciale dell'opera d'arte che finisce per oscurarne il valore semantico e simbolico (Santagata, 1998; Throsby 1999). Questo approccio disegna i contorni di una pratica artistica dove l'artista è alla mercé del giudizio di galleristi, curatori, critici. Nel mercato dell'arte, la sfida principale deriva dall'eccesso di informazioni piuttosto che dalla mancanza di esse, un fenomeno che contrasta con le dinamiche di asimmetria informativa tipiche di altri settori (Trimarchi, 2004; Zorloni, 2013; Beckert and Rossel, 2013). E, così, l'opera d'arte diventa strumento utilitaristico, costretta dentro ai confini di un mondo serrato, controllato, governato da un gruppo ristretto di *gatekeepers*. Un sistema che costringe l'artista a sacrificare la sperimentazione per costruire un network (Sacco, 2005) che avrà il potere di contribuire alla validazione dell'opera e all'andamento delle sue quotazioni (Frey and Pommerehne, 1989).

Lo stato dell'arte degli studi economici e umanistici del mercato dell'arte, così come i bisogni espressi da artisti contemporanei, dal pubblico e dal non-pubblico, evidenziano chiaramente l'urgenza di superare un sistema consolidato e ormai d'ostacolo alla totale diffusione artistica e culturale dell'opera. Esiste, infatti, una larga parte di produzione contemporanea che scavalca le barriere del mercato, basando le proprie pratiche sulla produzione di valore artistico (Sharon, 1979) personale (Wright, 2024) e sociale (Grodach, 2010). Si tratta della produzione artistica convenzionalmente definita come indipendente.

Da queste premesse nasce la necessità di sviluppare una ricerca che si interroghi su come gli spazi artistici indipendenti reinventino le logiche del mercato dell'arte attraverso nuove pratiche artistiche e organizzative. Lo studio si propone dunque di esplorare le caratteristiche economico-organizzative, i profili istituzionali e i rapporti con il territorio degli spazi artistici indipendenti per metterne a fuoco le lezioni emergenti.

L'esplorazione si sviluppa attraverso tre questioni le cui risposte costruiscono la risposta alla domanda principale: In che modo gli spazi indipendenti ridefiniscono i confini tra mercato, settore pubblico e sfera civile nella produzione culturale contemporanea? La letteratura storico-artistica ed economico-culturale definisce questi spazi "indipendenti" in quanto espressione della reazione alle dinamiche espositive e commerciali imposte dal mercato. Una concezione che, tuttavia, rischia di trascurare le caratteristiche di queste pratiche che si dimostrano per l'appunto indipendenti dal mercato. In che modo gli spazi artistici indipendenti organizzano la produzione culturale attraverso l'uso collettivo, la co-creazione e la governance situazionale?

L'attenzione al contesto che regola e determina l'origine e lo sviluppo delle pratiche artistiche indipendenti ha un ruolo maggiore nella letteratura che guarda agli spazi artistici informali da un punto di vista della dimensione urbana e dei loro rapporti con il contesto urbano. Questi studi aggiungono ai precedenti e aiutano a formulare la seconda questione. Si tratta di una domanda che imposta una ricerca mirata all'osservazione delle dinamiche urbane, ma che non trascura come queste pratiche restino sempre legate alla sperimentazione artistica, prima che sociale: in che modo queste pratiche generano e negoziano valori che sfuggono ai tradizionali quadri di valutazione economici o politici?

La terza questione è legata ai profili istituzionali e al contesto. La definizione di spazio indipendente, che deriva dagli studi economici e umanistici, pone un importante interrogativo: Quali condizioni di contesto (urbane, sociali, politiche)

favoriscono o limitano queste modalità alternative di produzione culturale? Un concetto, quello di “indipendenza”, importante perché porta con sé questioni ideologiche (l’indipendenza artistica) ma anche economiche (l’indipendenza dalle logiche commerciali del mercato e, quindi, anche dai fondi pubblici).

Nel momento in cui la revisione della letteratura e le domande che essa fa emergere toccano evidentemente aree che vanno oltre il mero valore commerciale dell’opera d’arte, si rivela indispensabile l’adozione di una cornice analitica specifica per guidare l’esplorazione empirica capace di tener conto di tutti i valori. Dopo una revisione della letteratura economica e umanistica dalla quale sono emerse le suddette questioni, e una conseguente revisione del valore associati al bene culturale, viene costruita la cornice del *value-based approach* (Klamer, 2016). Questa introduce la necessità di riconoscere l’esistenza di fattori molteplici per la valutazione e valorizzazione del prodotto creativo. La cornice, basata sul riconoscimento di cinque sfere valoriali (market, governance, cultural, social, *oikos*), ha guidato la costruzione dell’indagine. Viene inoltre delineata la metodologia applicata a uno studio di caso singolo, per poi presentarne il contesto legato al mercato dell’arte e ai processi di rigenerazione urbana. E vengono infine presentati i risultati, che pongono le basi per la discussione conclusiva.

L’analisi si è svolta attraverso l’osservazione delle pratiche del Collettivo Bastione, un gruppo di artisti attivi in uno spazio indipendente nella città di Torino. Oggi, la loro pratica ha luogo a Villa Rey, un edificio del seicento che sorge sulla collina torinese, data in concessione dal comune di Torino all’Associazione Villa dell’Arte che ha effettuato i restauri e collabora con Associazione Bastione per la promozione di eventi legati all’arte, alla musica e alla performance. Bastione è uno spazio di ricerca che ospita e promuove giovani realtà artistiche contemporanee, è un luogo di incontro e di scambio tra diverse personalità con l’obiettivo di valorizzare la proposta culturale nella città di Torino. Nasce come collettivo artistico nel 2017 all’interno degli spazi del Bastione San Maurizio dal

quale prende il nome. La pratica del Bastione sorge durante un'occupazione in uno degli edifici che compongono la Cavallerizza Reale, in un Garittono del 1670, collocato nel centro storico di Torino e tuttora in parziale stato di abbandono.

È in questa dimensione multiforme di orizzontalità e verticalità, di stanziamento e movimento, di ricircolo e trasformazione che può collocarsi l'esperienza del collettivo. Il lavoro di cura e riqualificazione svolto presso lo storico edificio del Bastione San Maurizio ha fin da subito messo in luce lo spirito degli artisti, spinti dalla necessità di rigenerare un luogo che fosse rappresentazione fisica di una comune esigenza. L'occupazione è stata dichiarazione di affermazione, volontà di porre un segno autodeterminante che non si dissolvesse nel silenzio. Lo stato di abbandono e precarietà del luogo, percepito come riflesso di un sentimento, è stato per gli artisti stimolo di racconto e raccordo fra luoghi e persone, possibilità di cambiare la stessa prospettiva del fare arte. L'identificazione con il Bastione San Maurizio ha determinato nel collettivo una metodologia che si distacca dall'indipendenza autoriale e dall'esposizione conforme al sistema artistico strutturato e gerarchico. Aprendosi così a una pluralità di linguaggi, la processualità creativa è diventata linfa vitale di una condivisione che ha azionato lo spazio in ogni sua forma¹.

Dunque, Associazione Bastione è: da una parte, i 15 artisti che componevano il gruppo (oggi 10) si conoscono all'Accademia Albertina, alle prese con i primi tentativi di trovare una via d'accesso al mercato dell'arte. Dall'altra, è pratica informale in uno spazio occupato da artisti visivi, performativi, teatranti e musicisti. Oltre alla restituzione di molteplici progetti artistici, alcuni tra gli artisti del collettivo presentano le loro tesi di laurea tra le mura occupate, esperienze e attività che saranno costretti ad interrompere dopo lo sgombero della Cavallerizza Reale. È proprio nei tessuti mnemonici che ora si custodisce l'esperienza del Bastione San

¹ Testo di Eleonora Fascetta.

Maurizio, la cui attività, ormai conclusa, prova a rinascere in altri luoghi. Dopo lo sgombero, nel 2020 il collettivo ha infatti formulato il suo statuto con il desiderio di portare avanti il progetto. Dal 2019, anno dello sgombero, i ragazzi di Bastione continuano la loro pratica senza uno spazio e nel frattempo si costituiscono in associazione. È qui che, dopo un primo momento di assestamento, la loro pratica artistica diviene matura e più consapevole. La pratica passata, fondamentale a porre le basi per quella presente, era stata guidata da un approccio transitorio, dovuto allo stato di occupazione e all'impossibilità di dialogare con le istituzioni. A Villa Rey, invece, prende avvio una pratica formale, da cui deriva la naturale urgenza di pianificazione, strategia, organizzazione e dialogo

La ricerca empirica condotta nel corso del 2024 ha dato risposte alle domande di ricerca, chiarendo i rapporti di causa ed effetto tra il mercato, le strutture urbane e il concetto di indipendenza. Per quanto riguarda il rapporto con il mercato, la pratica di Bastione nasce come ricollocamento necessario rispetto agli spazi offerti dall'Accademia. Nel corso degli anni trascorsi in Accademia, gli artisti stabiliscono un primo contatto con le dinamiche di mercato: contatto che anima in loro un naturale distacco nei confronti di alcune strutture di quel sistema. Tuttavia, la causa scatenante che porta a un temporaneo distacco dall'Accademia è più concreta, ovvero la mancanza di spazi e la difficoltà di relazionarsi con le strutture e i network del mercato. A questo riguardo, la Cavallerizza e il Bastione San Maurizio si rivelano i contesti più adatti per avviare una sperimentazione artistica in uno spazio abbandonato e a contatto con diverse discipline. Uno spazio dove la libertà offerta dal contesto e l'informalità delle relazioni si pongono come degne sostitute delle dinamiche di mercato.

Qui entra in gioco il rapporto con lo spazio e con la comunità urbana. Bastione sviluppa una pratica artistica incentrata sulla cura degli spazi, che promuove processi di riqualificazione degli spazi pubblici abbandonati attraverso interventi di restauro architettonico artistico (una pratica internazionale riconosciuta e

consolidata, che trova la sua maggiore espressione in esempi come Inhotim in Brasile). La cura degli spazi diviene premessa fondamentale per la creazione di una comunità, che si forma intorno a quegli spazi dove Bastione realizza i propri progetti artistici. Si tratta di eventi che uniscono le arti visive, performative e musicali, e che inaugurano una pratica artistica che fa sfumare i concetti convenzionali di creazione artistica (individuale, in uno studio) e di fruizione (il format della mostra in un museo).

Chiude il quadro la concezione che Bastione ha della sua pratica al Bastione San Maurizio prima e a Villa Rey oggi. Per gli artisti, la definizione di indipendenza è del tutto plasmata dalle logiche del mercato. Il concetto non definisce una pratica inserita in un determinato contesto, quanto un distacco ideologico dal mercato. Invece, ogni pratica artistica informale si rivela unica nella sua specie esattamente perché è il contesto a determinarne forme e indirizzi. Piuttosto, torna utile parlare di autonomia, un concetto capace di delineare i confini di un'attività artistica libera da imposizioni, ma anche libera di non ritenersi *indipendente* da finanziamenti.

I risultati dell'analisi portano alla formulazione di conclusioni generali che contribuiscono a conoscere e interpretare i valori alla base dell'organizzazione di pratiche informali e autonome. L'ultima parte della tesi presenta le implicazioni per le politiche culturali dedicate alla creazione contemporanea. Da notare che si tratta di pratiche che si fondano sul bisogno di:

- Una rete di infrastrutture (gli spazi, le tecnologie, le connessioni);
- Una struttura organizzativa informale, che può diventare risorsa economica e relazionale se valorizzata. Si basa sulla trasversalità dei ruoli, l'apertura al confronto, la collaborazione interna ed esterna e il dinamismo;
- L'autonomia artistica e la ricerca di fondi che la rendano sostenibile;

- Il dialogo con l'amministrazione locale e le fondazioni bancarie, per avere la possibilità di narrare la propria pratica, anziché incanalarla nelle categorie imposte dai bandi e dalla burocrazia;
- L'impatto sulla società attraverso l'attivazione di processi di rigenerazione urbana e lo sviluppo di comunità.

Per quanto i risultati della ricerca siano specifici soprattutto al contesto di Associazione Bastione, essi contribuiscono a una comprensione più generale delle pratiche artistiche informali e di come queste stabiliscano relazioni con il mercato, con le dinamiche urbane e con le istituzioni. In quest'ottica, le pratiche indipendenti non si presentano più come anomalie, ma diventano superamento dei modelli convenzionali verso un paradigma ancora da definire.

Questo lavoro si è posto l'obiettivo di dare voce alla pratica di Bastione e soprattutto alla loro visione. A monte di tutto risiede, come in ogni lavoro di ricerca individuale, una motivazione personale. Spero, con questa tesi, di contribuire a tornare a dare valore all'arte come pratica esistenziale proprio in quanto espressione trascendentale dell'essere e risposta incisiva all'urgenza di rappresentazione del sé.

Foreword

During the presentation of my research proposal at a seminar one day, a professor of Economics showed actual surprise at the kind of dynamics I was discussing. It was not clear to him that my objective was to situate the research beyond the sphere of the market. From his perspective, the actions of artists operating beyond the market were still part of a market where transactions must occur. I tried to clarify that in the artistic practice I had been observing and analysing there were no transactions apart from home-made food, beer and donations. He argued that the economy of a space could not be analysed if there were no transactions beyond beer. At that point, I felt somehow offended. In the days that followed, however, reflection on what had happened revealed a significant discrepancy in our discussion. I was discussing an economy based on a system of values that exist beyond the market, where practices can be assimilated to that of a family, friendship or home, where market value is just one part of a larger picture. In reality, markets are temporary structures, and it is time to acknowledge that people have existed and continue to exist in the absence of such structures, but still live in what we might define an economy.

Once, while I was on a beach in Kenya, I spoke with a man selling jewelry to tourists. I asked if he had any earrings, and he showed me a variety of large ones. I wanted to buy a pair for my mom and mentioned that she liked small earrings. He put away his jewelry and began making custom earrings right in front of me. I was surprised by this attitude. He stayed with me, cutting a stone to my specifications—or rather, to my mom's preferences, even though he had never met her. It was a deep and intense experience that demonstrated the value of craftsmanship and personal exchange. We also put different values on these transactions, filtered through our different cultures. The transaction itself was worth 2 euros, which, if we were to rate it from 0 to 10, would be close to 0 for me and close to 10 for him.

So, who determines the commercial value of the transaction? For me, those 2 euros were equivalent to one or two fewer coffees; for him, it was a dinner for his whole family. While he made the earrings, he talked about his large family, how they brought food, how they shared meals, and how their diet varied with the seasons. They were cousins, brothers, parents, and grandparents, each taking turns to provide food, ensuring everyone ate every day.

As I write this, I focus on his face and words, resisting the urge to filter these concepts through my Western, neoliberal perspective with terms like “economy,” “organization,” and “planning.” For him, it was just the way he lived and did the right thing (Klamer, 2017). It seems to me that many people in the contemporary Western world, myself included, use market structures to simplify the complexity of reality. Concepts like demand, supply, impact, and externality categorise and simplify our interactions with reality. The term “economy” itself implies a construct that the Kenyan beachboy would never mention.

However, this was not a transaction as standard economists would define it; it was much more. What he gave me during the “transaction” went far beyond a mere commercial exchange. There were a number of values in that exchange that were beyond market value. First, his act of making earrings specifically for my mom is something we in Europe attach extreme commercial value to, similar to how we value limited edition shoes. However, in my case, it still only costed 2 euros. Second, the time he took to make the earrings, which is highly valued in our society, was given freely. Thirdly, during that time, we exchanged cultural knowledge, building an intercultural relationship. In my country, such experiences come at a high cost, yet in Kenya, they were all free. After saying goodbye, I felt puzzled because it was unusual for me to make sense of this “transaction.” I spent 2 euros but felt immensely happy, satisfied, enriched, and had two beautiful earrings for my mom.

This is what exchange means to me, and this is the idea I want to convey in this dissertation on independent art spaces. It may seem strange to write a thesis on the economics of culture and the arts while distancing myself from the contemporary art market itself and the standard understanding of economy and economics.

However, my purpose is to discuss different economies and a new cultural economics, where values go beyond transactions in a market. My ultimate aim is to contribute to discourses on diverse economies and a new cultural economics, wherein multiple values transcend commercial transactions (Throsby, 2001, 2003; Klamer, 2003; Trimarchi, 2004; Throsby and Zednik, 2014; Klamer, 2016, 2017; Klamer et al., 2022). The intention here is to convey that independent artists exist and act beyond market structures and in accordance with their creative repertoire, with civic, social, relational and artistic goals, reinforcing the view that art is an exemplary realm for realising one's own identity (Dekker and Morea, 2023). From this perspective, it is crucial to acknowledge that the market sphere, where transactions and commercial values are conducted and established, represents only a part of the broader context. This is particularly evident in the case of visual artists, who are required by the contemporary art market system to deal with markets on a daily basis. The following pages examine the extent to which the practices that emerge in independent art spaces are aligned with the *zeitgeist* as they propose new paradigms, as opposed to the dictates of the standard market.

Introduction

Are artists going to change the world?

I think super rich people have a lot of faith in artists - which I think is unfair, really. Because they should be doing their bit as well. I mean, it's funny: you go to a lot of events where very rich people go on and on about this. Saying artists are superhumans, they are going to change our lives. These are people with maybe billions, people who actually are in a position to change the world - if they wanted to. But often what they do is just to collect art. If you are looking to artists to change the world, I think you're probably looking in the wrong direction. (Jeremy Deller, artist, interview for Designboom, 2024)

This research begins with a problem emerging from a systemic contradiction: while artists are frequently celebrated for their supposed transformative power within urban and cultural policy discourses, the infrastructures that govern artistic production often undermine their autonomy, visibility, and expressive potential. Contemporary art markets, in particular, rely on complex mechanisms of recognition, circulation, and institutional endorsement that disproportionately favor artists and works that align with dominant curatorial and commercial logics. As a result, artistic practices that are experimental, process-based, collaborative, or grounded in specific local contexts often remain peripheral to the official circuits of value creation.

The first chapter of this dissertation critically examines how value is constructed within the art market, focusing on the actors, networks, and institutions that shape recognition and exchange. Drawing on literature in cultural economics and art sociology, it becomes clear that while market visibility is a key driver of symbolic and economic capital, it tends to reward conformity over experimentation. Recognition accrues to artists whose work fits easily into formats that can circulate through galleries, fairs, and biennials—formats that can be framed, priced, and sold. In this system, curators, gallerists, and critics function as gatekeepers, constructing

value through selective filtering, often at the expense of less commodifiable forms of artistic labor. These dynamics reveal a key limitation in market-based approaches to cultural value: they obscure the diversity of contemporary artistic practices that operate outside the mainstream art world.

Building on this critique, the research shifts its focus: from examining how value is constructed within the market, to investigating where else artistic value is generated, and how. This pivot leads to the emergence of independent art spaces as critical sites of inquiry. Artist-led and often informally organized, these spaces challenge models of production and dissemination in the market. They foster alternative way of organization, embeddedness and experimentation that defy the logics of the market. For this reason, they provide a valuable opportunity to reconsider how value is produced and negotiated in the cultural field. For this reason, the thesis proposes a literature review of independent art spaces analyzed from a context-related perspective, including insight from urban studies, spatial sociology, and cultural policy (Chapter 2).

Literature as presented in chapter 1 and 2 offers critical insights into the institutional, historical and spatial dynamics of these spaces. Art-historical perspectives show how early independent initiatives emerged in resistance to the gallery system, often tied to broader political and ideological critiques. More recent studies focus on their organizational forms and social roles, noting their adaptability, networked structures, and resource precarity. However, studies have not yet addressed how these spaces generate and negotiate value across multiple dimensions, connecting both to market, to institutions and to civil society. To address this gap, the thesis introduces the Value-Based Approach (VBA) (Klamer, 2016) which provides a conceptual and analytical lens to explore the plurality of values (market, governance, social, personal, cultural) generated within independent art spaces. Therefore, the aim of the research is to develop a broader understanding of value creation in independent art space in order to contextualize their embeddedness in specific socio-urban conditions, while also considering their relationship with the market.

Building on these premises, the central research question guiding this research is:

- How do grassroots artistic practices reshape the boundaries between the market, the public sector, and the civil sphere in contemporary cultural production?

This question is explored through the following sub-questions:

1. In what ways do independent art spaces organize cultural production through collective use, co-creation, and situated governance?
2. How do these practices generate and negotiate value(s) that escape conventional economic or policy-driven evaluative frameworks?
3. What contextual conditions (urban, social, political) enable or constrain these alternative modes of cultural production?

To address these questions, the dissertation follows a qualitative, abductive research design structured across eight chapters. Chapter 1 reviews the literature on independent art spaces and their relationship to the market. Chapter 2 investigates the role of urban context and spatial transformation in shaping artistic practice. Chapter 3 introduces the concept of value in cultural economics and argues for the use of the VBA in studying cultural production. Chapter 4 operationalizes the VBA into analytical tools for fieldwork. Chapter 5 presents the methodology, which combines semi-structured interviews and participant observation. Chapter 6 maps Turin's artistic ecosystem to contextualize the case study and lay the ground for the third research question. Chapter 7 presents the research findings, organized around the main value spheres activated by Bastione's practice. Finally, Chapter 8 articulates a "value trail" that traces the evolving relationship between autonomy, collaboration, and recognition over time. It aims to offer a new perspective on how independent artistic initiatives produce value in relation to institutions, markets, and urban communities.

Chapter 1

Independent art spaces and the limits of the market

This chapter sets the stage for the thesis examining how the art market has historically shaped artistic production and why independent art spaces have emerged as situated responses to its structural limitations. The art market, while central to the distribution and recognition of visual artworks, is shaped by gatekeeping logics and exchange-based valuation that often exclude or marginalize forms of artistic labor that do not conform to its norms. As a result, many artists who seek to engage in experimental, community-driven, or process-based practices find themselves operating beyond its reach. In this context, independent art spaces have emerged as culturally embedded and context related alternatives to the market. These spaces, mostly artist-run, not-for-profit or informal practices, support forms of co-creation, horizontal governance, and situated value production that are shaped by context, relationship, and practice. Scholars have variously described these entities as “alternative,” “grassroots,” “artist-led,” or “informal” (Sharon, 1979; Blessi et al., 2011; Arthurs, 2012; Haghghat, 2020). This study begins by examining literature on the market and later connects it with literature that help explore their geographical, socio-political, and civic embeddedness (laying the foundation for the analysis of their social, personal, governance, and cultural spheres). This chapter is organized into three sections. Section 1.1 maps the evolution of key actors in the art market. Section 1.2 discusses recent transformations in the ecosystem, including digitalization, co-creation, and sustainability. Section 1.3 defines and situates independent art spaces within

literature, synthesizing both institutional and art-historical approaches to show why they demand new frameworks for understanding value and practice.

1.1 Actors in the market

The structure of the contemporary art market is rooted in a historical rejection of institutional orthodoxy, yet paradoxically has become increasingly institutionalized itself through commercial and financial consolidation. The late 19th-century rupture with the Académie des Beaux-Arts in France, catalyzed by figures such as Durand-Ruel, initiated a shift toward private mediation in the art world. However, this shift did not democratize access so much as reconfigure hierarchies of valuation through new forms of cultural intermediation—galleries, critics, collectors, and auction houses—which remain the principal gatekeepers of artistic legitimacy.

Rather than an open marketplace, the art ecosystem operates as a symbolic economy in which information asymmetries and barriers to entry structure visibility and value creation (Trimarchi, 2011; Quemin, 2013). While the proliferation of galleries, art fairs, and biennials since the 1970s has ostensibly diversified the field, these developments have often deepened commercial logics. Events such as Art Basel, for instance, exemplify the market's turn towards spectacle and investment platforms, where price setting and brand curation often supersede critical or aesthetic deliberation (Poli, 2015).

The discursive construction of the 'artist' within this ecosystem is particularly fraught. Artists are conceptualized as producers within a system that commodifies symbolic goods, yet their success is contingent not merely on the quality of their output but on their capacity to address opaque and exclusionary networks of influence. The economic and reputational capital necessary for sustainability is unevenly distributed, exacerbated by what Zorloni and Ardizzone (2016) identify as high barriers to both entry and visibility. Artists often engage in substantial relational labor to compensate for the lack of institutional support, and many are

compelled to seek supplementary income due to precarious market returns (Abbing, 2008; Comunian et al., 2011).

Despite their historical role in shaping artistic canons, academies have been largely sidelined within contemporary market dynamics. Their transformation into interdisciplinary, university-like institutions has not translated into influence within commercial circuits. This institutional decoupling highlights a broader tension between artistic formation and market relevance, with few studies directly assessing the academy's structural position in today's ecosystem (Boime, 1994; Abbing, 2008).

Auction houses, notably Sotheby's and Christie's, dominate the secondary market and play a critical role in translating symbolic value into economic capital (Chong, 2005). Their influence has expanded through their role as cultural tastemakers and market regulators, suggesting a formalization of speculative mechanisms within the art economy.

Collectors, both private and institutional, act as powerful actors in canon formation and market stabilization. Their dual role—as consumers and arbiters—confers them significant influence over trends, valuations, and institutional acquisitions. They also contribute to the privatization of cultural heritage through the proliferation of private foundations (Zorloni, 2019).

Art consultants, a relatively recent phenomenon, serve as intermediaries favoring the interests of collectors rather than artists. Their professionalization further institutionalizes speculative logics, as they advise on acquisitions with financial risk minimization in mind (Corradini, 2011). This reinforces the marginality of emerging artists, as consultants typically favor proven, market-validated work (Sacco, 2004).

Critics and curators function as symbolic gatekeepers, mediating between production and reception. However, their roles are increasingly complicated by platform fragmentation and digital dissemination, where institutional authority is often undermined by new modes of expertise and algorithmic visibility (Arora & Vermeulen, 2013). Curators, in particular, balance contradictory roles: as both

enablers of artistic experimentation and participants in the logics of brand-making and institutional prestige (Coleman, 2016).

Galleries, traditionally a pivotal platform for career development, are increasingly shaped by risk-averse practices and global hierarchies. While they facilitate the entry of artists into market circuits, they also act as gatekeepers that filter access based on perceived potential for economic return. The expansion of mega-galleries, such as those operated by Gagosian or Zwirner, further concentrates power and narrows the range of artist representation (Velthuis, 2003; Coslor et al., 2020).

Museums, although historically positioned as public custodians of cultural value, are not immune to the marketization of the art ecosystem. Their dual function—as educational institutions and market validators—places them in a contradictory position. While they offer critical space for less commodified artistic practices, their structural rigidity and Western-centric canon remain problematic. The Kunsthalle model has been proposed as a more flexible institutional form better aligned with contemporary art's ephemeral and processual nature (Shvartzberg, 2012).

Fairs and biennials reflect broader shifts toward event-based cultural economies. Despite their discursive framing as sites of international exchange or critical engagement, their structural logic is predominantly commercial. This is particularly evident in the exponential growth of art fairs since the 1990s and the increasing convergence of exhibition and sales logics (Bethwaite & Kangas, 2018). These platforms often reproduce global hierarchies rather than challenge them, reaffirming Western dominance even as they expand into so-called peripheral geographies (Belting, 2012).

The dynamics of the contemporary art market are visually represented in Figure 1.1, which is derived from the literature review². This is helpful in examining the artist's interactions with all of the actors.

Figure 1.1. Network of exchanges in the contemporary art ecosystem, based on the literature.
Source: author's own elaboration.

The structure of the contemporary art market constitutes an essential backdrop for understanding the positioning and value negotiations of independent art spaces. While often represented as a decentralized or pluralistic field, the art market is in fact shaped by longstanding hierarchies and institutional logics that continue to mediate access, visibility and legitimacy. Its historical trajectory, beginning with

² Art fairs and biennials were not incorporated into the ecosystem depicted in Figure 1.1, as they do not inherently contribute to the daily dynamics.

the late 19th-century rupture from the Académie des Beaux-Arts and the emergence of private dealers like Durand-Ruel, marked a shift from state-sanctioned models of valuation to a system grounded in cultural intermediation. This shift reconfigured gatekeeping functions through new market actors—galleries, critics, collectors, and auction houses—who continue to play a decisive role in determining artistic value (Quemin, 2013; Trimarchi, 2011).

The art ecosystem operates as a symbolic economy characterized by information asymmetries, relational dependencies, and high barriers to entry. The rise of global art fairs, mega-galleries, and private foundations has intensified commercial and speculative logics while narrowing the space for experimentation and alternative practices (Poli, 2015; Coslor et al., 2020). The increasing professionalization of art consultants and collectors reflect a financialization of the field, where visibility is increasingly tied to brand-building, risk minimization, and strategic positioning. In this context, artistic success becomes less a function of creative merit than of one's capacity to access and navigate opaque circuits of cultural and economic capital (Zorloni and Ardizzone, 2016; Abbing, 2008).

This configuration deeply affects the figure of the artist, who is expected to perform simultaneously as creator, entrepreneur and networked actor. Art academies and alternative institutions once held formative influence, but today their role has been increasingly decoupled from market relevance (Boime, 1994; Abbing, 2008). Moreover, the expansion of curatorial and institutional frameworks has not resolved these tensions but, in many cases, has reinforced existing hierarchies and institutional norms, albeit in more discursively progressive terms (Coleman, 2016; Arora & Vermeylen, 2013).

1.2 Latest trends in the contemporary art ecosystem: The technological vs. community-oriented turn of the market

Rapid shifts and emergent trends are the defining characteristics of the contemporary art ecosystem, which transforms the processes of art production and

dissemination. The educational and professional dynamics within the art system have undergone a significant transformation, which is indicative of broader societal changes (Velthuis and Curioni, 2015). Throughout history, art academies have been instrumental in the development and advancement of artists. However, their influence has diminished, and the art world now increasingly depends on networks and community-based approaches to support artistic vocations (Abbing, 2008; Seifert et al., 2005). This change serves to emphasize the importance of robust networks and suggests a departure from traditional institutional pathways. In addition to personal networks, residencies, and national/international networks, online platforms and onsite facilities also play a critical role in the support of contemporary artists. They offer artists invaluable resources for their creative practice, facilitating creative exchange, professional development, and increased visibility. Residencies offer artists the opportunity to cultivate their work in a dedicated environment, frequently in stimulating new settings, thereby fostering cross-cultural dialogue and innovation (Badham, 2017; Lehman, 2017). Additionally, they serve as sanctuaries for creativity, allowing artists to interact with a diverse array of perspectives and practices that can significantly impact their artistic output (Renard and Zanella, 2021). International and national networks, such as TransArtists in the Netherlands, facilitate the establishment of connections between artists and global art communities, thereby promoting collaboration and exposure to new audiences. These networks can facilitate career advancement by providing access to critical discourse, funding, and exhibitions, as well as residencies, which are essential components of the art ecosystem (TransArtists, 2024).

The art market has been significantly affected by the emergence of digital technologies. Online galleries have become substantial participants in the art market, providing artists with unparalleled access to global audiences and collectors (Ivancic et al., 2016; Habelsberger and Bhansing, 2021). Platforms like Instagram have had a significant impact on the consumption and dissemination of art by enabling direct connections between artists and audiences (MacDowall and Budge,

2021; Budge and Burness, 2018). Additionally, the art market is being disrupted by new technologies, including AI, blockchain, and cryptocurrency, which are providing innovative methods for purchasing, selling, and authenticating art (Radermecker and Ginsburgh, 2023).

The advent of contemporary media, such as street art, is challenging the format and boundaries of museums by presenting a dynamic form of expression that challenges norms and engages audiences in unconventional ways (Blanché, 2015; Costa and Lopes, 2015). In addition, the Museum of Contemporary Art (MoCA) in Los Angeles is a prime example of a museum that is being challenged by new formats that extend exhibitions to the outskirts of cities and engage with urban communities. Additionally, artist-run and independent spaces have emerged as essential platforms for artists who operate outside of the traditional institutional framework, enabling them to work towards urban communities and experiment (Grodach, 2010; Malatjie, 2013). In these formats, the concept of co-creation is emphasized in contrast to that of the passive audience (Dekker and Morea, 2023). Additionally, artists are becoming more cognizant of social, political, and environmental issues, and activism is a fusion of artistic and political practices that is designed to address concerns such as gender equality and environmental issues (Zebracki, 2020). This trend demonstrates the ability of art to influence public discourse and serve as a vehicle for social transformation. Additionally, there is a growing acknowledgment that the contemporary art ecosystem is primarily viewed through a Western perspective, which restricts our comprehension of global practices. For instance, the African and Indian art markets are increasingly incorporating Western practices as a result of globalization, which reflects the impact of these broader economic and cultural changes (Belting, 2012). Nevertheless, art is also evolving in independent art spaces in non-Western countries (Chun, 2016; Gurney, 2023). Furthermore, museums and art galleries that prioritize the incorporation of sustainable practices into their operational procedures and programming are becoming increasingly relevant to the discourse surrounding cultural sustainability. This involves the development of exhibits that address

pressing social and environmental issues, the promotion of diversity and inclusion, and the engagement with local and global communities (Kagan, 2014; York, 2014; Evensen and Stafseng, 2024).

The dynamics of the contemporary art ecosystem are visually represented in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2 Evolving dynamics in the contemporary art ecosystem. Source: author's own elaboration.

1.3 Independent art spaces from a market perspective

The structure and dynamics of the contemporary art market tend to privilege mobility, scale, and visibility, often excluding artists whose practices are embedded in local contexts or informed by place-based forms of engagement. For these situated artists—those whose work is closely tied to specific communities, territories, or urban conditions—the market rarely offers meaningful opportunities for recognition or sustainability. This disconnection is symptomatic of a system that fails to recognize processual, horizontal, collaborative or context-responsive practices.

Recent trends in the art market reinforce this trajectory. While the field has expanded through new platforms, e.g. art fairs, online marketplaces and blockchain-based systems, these innovations often replicate or exacerbate existing hierarchies. The consolidation of mega-galleries, the rise of art consultants and the financialization of the secondary market have further narrowed the space for experimentation, while public institutions, historically a counterbalance to commercial forces, have become increasingly entangled with market logics. Even platforms that appear to democratize access, e.g. Instagram or artist-led NFTs, tend to privilege visibility over depth and amplify competitive dynamics (Velthuis and Curioni, 2015; Radermecker and Ginsburgh, 2023).

Against this backdrop, independent and artist-run spaces play a critical role in enabling alternative modes of cultural production. These spaces offer infrastructures for artists operating outside commercial circuits, creating room for collective work, artistic research and civic engagement. They may not entirely escape market pressures, yet they offer different forms of value creation that challenge the predominantly market logics of the dominant art economy. Their role is also transformative: they provide concrete alternatives to market-dominated models and contribute to a plural and situated cultural ecosystem.

1.3.1 Institutional and market studies

Against the backdrops of the market (1.1), independent art spaces articulate alternative responses. They often arise as critical infrastructures that question dominant valuation mechanisms while experimenting with new forms of cultural production and engagement. Their significance lies in their capacity to reconfigure the relations between artistic practice, community and value. These spaces foreground forms of collective use, informal governance and situated co-creation that challenge the logics of the market previously described.

This analysis employs the definition of independent art spaces, which, in comparison to other definitions such as "art space" and "informal space," provides the most comprehensive framework for understanding their role within the visual arts and the broader art market (Vorobeva, 2022). A relevant aspect of the contemporary art system is the emergence of independent art spaces, which operate beyond the limitations of conventional market structures. This phenomenon can be traced back to the 1960s (Sharon, 1979). Despite their historical relevance, research into the management practices and institutional dynamics of these spaces remains limited, particularly in non-American contexts (Blessi et al., 2011). The available literature on these spaces indicates that they are typically artist-run, not-for-profit venues that aim to foster collaboration and bridge local and international cultures (Sharon, 1979; Blessi et al., 2011; Arthurs, 2012; Dettere and Nannucci, 2012; Haghighat, 2020). These spaces serve as public platforms and workspaces for artists, facilitating creativity and experimental practices while also contributing to the socio-economic development of their surrounding communities (Arthurs, 2012). In studies on institutional dynamics, the rise of independent art spaces is often interpreted as a response to the commercial framework imposed by the traditional art market (Sharon, 1979). Despite their relatively minor role in the formal art market, due to limited resources and visibility compared to market-dominant actors (Blessi et al., 2011; Arthurs, 2012), their absence from conventional art market studies (Działek, 2021) undermines their importance. Independent art spaces provide indispensable settings for artistic experimentation, unconstrained by the economic, physical, and cultural limits imposed by market

forces (Komarova, 2020). Therefore, they perform a vital yet underresearched function within the institutional framework of the contemporary art system.

From an institutional standpoint, the cultural economy investigates the organisational dynamics and funding mechanisms of cultural organisations. The research indicates that these non-profit spaces are able to flourish for two main reasons. In some countries, they benefit from the networks of artist mobility and residency programmes. For example, in Canada, this has been demonstrated by Blessi et al. (2011) and Arthurs (2012). Moreover, in the majority of cases, these organisations are not-for-profit, which allows for the professional activity and development of artists who, for a variety of reasons, are unable or not primarily interested in achieving a high level of market recognition. This leaves space for independent research and practice (Jackson, 2004). This is particularly the case with regard to independent art spaces. Since their emergence in the 1970s, independent spaces have presented a challenge to museums in their pursuit of new audiences. This is particularly evident in the case of contemporary art, which requires a more flexible and open approach to its presentation. The primary challenge facing these spaces is the issue of funding, which has constrained their growth and expansion. Such establishments typically engage in modest commercial activities, including the occasional sale of works on display to collectors and, on a more systematic basis, the organisation of charity auctions of artworks. In order to sustain their activities, they engage in fundraising initiatives, seeking private partners and sponsors. Ultimately, they submit applications for public funding, both on a regular, periodic basis and for specific projects (Blessi et al., 2011).

The chronological origins of independent spaces in relation to the art scene can be traced back to the 1960s and 1970s in New York and other American cities (Sharon, 1979). Concurrently, analogous spaces began to emerge in Toronto and Montreal, particularly as a consequence of cultural, political, and gender movements. These spaces were primarily managed by artist collectives, with the objective of facilitating experimental research and hosting exhibitions by invited artists. These spaces were financed by the artists themselves and by public national

and international subsidies (Blessi et al., 2011; Arthurs, 2012; Yıldız, 2020). In general, independent arts spaces serve as a venue for artistic experimentation, offering an alternative to more institutionalised settings (Chun, 2016). Experimental art spaces provide an alternative to commercial galleries, government-funded venues, private galleries and museums, operating under a different set of rules that challenge traditional institutions. By challenging the conventional white-cube format, these alternative spaces facilitate discourse on alternative art programming, collaborative art-making, and the necessity of institutional funding to sustain such spaces (Malatjie, 2013). When funded, such spaces provide artists with the resources to maintain their livelihoods and workspaces, facilitate professional development, and offer opportunities for networking and engagement with the commercial art market, while maintaining their independence (Blessi et al., 2011; Arthurs, 2012; Yıldız, 2020). They facilitate the formation of a unified community and promote interdisciplinary collaboration. Notwithstanding the constraints imposed by limited resources, they sustain dynamic networks (Santagata, 2009). A distinctive feature of non-profit organisations operating in the artistic and cultural domain that have emerged since the early 2000s is the dialogical relationship they establish between their project activities and the context in which they operate. Delfini (2009) posits that the local territory, its socio-cultural history and the community that animates it exert a significant influence on the project activity of the spaces.

The body of existing literature presents a range of perspectives on the capacity of independent art spaces to develop networks. Some commentators regard these spaces as somewhat exclusive, with a primary focus on artistic production and limited engagement beyond the cultural sector (Blessi et al., 2011; Byrne et al., 2006). Such institutions typically cater primarily to professionals engaged in the visual arts, exhibiting underdeveloped ties to local economies and a relatively weak presence at major contemporary art events. The high turnover of staff and financial constraints act as significant impediments to the development of robust programming and the implementation of strategic planning. Consequently, they

encounter difficulties in establishing long-term partnerships. In order to enhance their role, it would be beneficial for these spaces to engage in more robust collaborations with prominent local institutions, as well as adopt more innovative approaches to management, fundraising, and public engagement. For example, they could attract established artists seeking authentic environments and facilitate the introduction of contemporary art to new audiences through educational programmes. Moreover, they could leverage urban policies to repurpose industrial premises as cultural facilities and engage younger, digitally proficient audiences through multimedia artistic initiatives. Nevertheless, several challenges persist, including a dearth of professional management expertise, venue constraints, and rental vulnerabilities. In the absence of more profound engagement with local stakeholders and younger audiences, these spaces may become marginalised and financially precarious. As evidenced by studies on the contexts of Toronto and Montreal (Blessi et al., 2011; Byrne et al., 2006), radical restructuring may be imperative to ensure the long-term relevance and sustainability of these spaces.

Conversely, a body of literature has identified the potential for artists to establish their practice on the basis of a system of friendship. Once their artistic influence and polymorphous identity are acknowledged, their activity is interpreted as making a significant contribution to the discourse on social art or socially engaged art practice (Hope 2017). In particular, it is their capacity to create cultural ecologies based on friendships that is seen as a distinctive feature of their activity and practice (Wright, 2019). The notion of care is integral to contemporary independent art spaces, where artists frequently act as caretakers not only of physical spaces but also of communal and relational environments. This aspect of care, explored extensively in the literature on socially engaged art (Jackson, 2004; Wright, 2024), is central to understanding the evolving role of independent art collectives. Furthermore, their political proclivities are acknowledged, given their tendency to operate outside of elitist settings and within urban contexts. Given the pivotal role of space in their practice, they contribute to placemaking and public discourse at multiple levels, constantly negotiating between competing forces (D'Ettorre, 2023;

Wright, 2024). These elements – namely, space, friendship and political discourse – are strongly associated with discourses on urban development.

1.3.2 An art history perspective

Research on institutional dynamics offers critical insights into how these spaces function within the broader art system. An investigation of research in art history is especially beneficial for comprehending the manner in which the dynamics of these spaces have evolved over time and how, despite their initial opposition to commercial frameworks, they are in fact connected to broader market dynamics. An examination of art history offers valuable insights into the transition of these spaces from radical alternatives to established institutions to a more complex engagement with the art market, reflecting shifts in both the artistic and economic landscapes. This historical perspective facilitates an understanding of how independent spaces continue to navigate their relationships with market forces while maintaining their distinct roles as sites of innovation and resistance. According to art historians, the origins of independent art spaces are often traced back to the movements that emerged in the 1960s and 1970s (Rosati, 2012). In these years, the art world joined the revolutionary wave that swept across Europe and North America in the late 1960s. This period was marked by a series of protests and denunciations, including those against civil inequalities, the Vietnam War, and the new social and economic order that emerged as a result of dominant capitalism. Initially, the art world expressed its opposition to museum institutions through these protests. The targeting of museums served to raise a number of interrelated issues, including those pertaining to artists' rights, opposition to the Vietnam War, racism, and ultimately, sexism. Additionally, the correlation between aesthetics and corporate finance, as well as imperialism, came under scrutiny (Lippard, 1965). Artists adopted an active stance against the prevailing political, social and ideological structures, utilising their creative output to express dissent and revolt against a system they perceived as unrepresentative and in need of transformation. While artists were calling for the art world to be activated against injustice and

inequality, museums were becoming increasingly neutral on political and social issues. From the late 1960s onwards, they were targeted by organisational collectives such as the Art Workers Coalition.

Figure 1.3 Photo from the group exhibition opening 112Workshop/112 Greene Street, New York, 197. Source: White Columns.

The white cube represented the idea of art as a marketable commodity, which artists, in particular, were faced with. They sought to reorient their focus toward the creative process itself, which they perceived to possess intrinsic artistic value. During this time, the emergence of installations, environments, and performances was observed. These works were ephemeral, difficult to document, and represented a departure from the conventional, detached relationship between viewer and artwork. These non-traditional artistic expressions were particularly well received

within the official gallery and museum circuit. The inaugural spaces, situated within derelict and degraded edifices, exemplify the artists' unconventional approach. The initial decision to work in spaces with aesthetic characteristics that contrasted with the aseptic and uncontaminated nature of the white cube, although based on economic necessity, was nevertheless informed by a political and ideological perspective. This reflected a rejection of the artistic model proposed by the white cube and a consideration of art in terms of market value. In these spaces, artists were afforded the opportunity to use the available resources, including the physical structure, furnishings and raw materials, as their primary medium. This approach was exemplified by the artist Matta Clark, who created a hole in the floor to plant a cherry tree (Ault, 2002). In these locations, the artists were able to exercise their creative freedom and spontaneity, working without the constraints of external conditions or impositions. They were able to work and collaborate without any aesthetic or spatial limitations.

Chapter 2

Independent art spaces and urban contexts

This chapter explores the spatial embeddedness of independent art spaces and their entanglement with urban processes, regeneration frameworks, and local community dynamics. While Chapter 1 situated these spaces in relation to the art market and broader structures of artistic labor, the present chapter shifts the focus to their geographical, socio-political, and civic embeddedness. It examines how independent art spaces intervene in urban environments as cultural producers but also as civic actors who shape, and are shaped by, the socio-spatial conditions of the city.

Building on the literature concerning independent art spaces within the art market (Chapter 1), this chapter paves the way for a broader definition, taking into account other streams of literature that focus more on urban structures. This definition is provided at the end of the chapter and can be found in the glossary under 'independent'. The intention is to avoid defining independence as a fixed institutional position and instead conceptualize it as a dynamic, situated condition that prioritizes experimentation, collective governance and spatial reappropriation, all within the context of shifting urban, social and political constraints.

The aim of this chapter is to examine, through a literature review, how independent artistic practices generate forms of value through their situated use of space, informal governance, and modes of co-creation. These dynamics often intersect with broader policy agendas—e.g. urban regeneration, social inclusion, or sustainability—but they also exceed these frameworks producing social and

cultural value that is not easily measurable and traceable by current monitoring tools. Drawing on insights from urban studies, spatial sociology, and cultural policy, the chapter develops an analytical lens that will inform the subsequent empirical analysis.

To do so, the chapter is structured in four parts. Section 2.1 reviews the urban connections of independent art spaces, drawing from theoretical frameworks that situate these practices within wider processes of city-making, post-industrial transition, and cultural-led regeneration. Section 2.2 then turns to the role of artists in urban transformation and community development, highlighting how creative practices intersect with urban regeneration discourses and contribute to socio-cultural ecosystems. Section 2.3 explores how independent art spaces have been studied within urban contexts, focusing on their organizational forms, proximity to communities, and spatial distribution. Finally, Section 2.4 synthesizes these perspectives to propose a working definition of independent art spaces that bridges their market disconnection and their embeddedness in urban and civic processes—thus reinforcing the need for a broader conceptual framework capable of accounting for their diverse value contributions.

2.1 Urban theories and cultural practice

The urban connections of independent art spaces are being increasingly emphasized in recent studies. The previous chapter's literature review contextualized these spaces within and beyond the contemporary art market, examining their historical significance, political relationships, and organizational structures. As the majority of research on independent art spaces—whether they are referred to as art spaces, informal or independent spaces, grassroots initiatives, etc.—emphasizes their connection to physical locations and the urban landscape, this review already suggests a strong urban link (Grodach, 2010, 2011; Malatjie, 2013; Działek, 2021). Urban studies are inextricably linked to the examination of independent art spaces, given their importance. More precisely, the discussions of

their urban connections are consistent with the broader discourse on the roles of artists and grassroots artistic practices in urban transformation and city-making (Murzyn-Kupisz and Działek, 2017; Zilberstein, 2019; Morea and Sabatini, 2023). These studies provide insights into the theoretical framework that defines artists' actions for urban vitality (Elliot et al., 2020), the implications for the creative and post-creative city (Miles, 2013; Zheng, 2021) and their impact on urban regeneration processes (Sharp et al., 2005; Zebracki, 2012; Lavanga, 2013). This analysis will facilitate the development of a specific framework for analyzing these spaces in relation to the urban context and urban communities, extending beyond their relationship to the art scene and the art market. Such a framework will help provide guidance and direction for fully recognizing the value and impact of these spaces.

2.2 The role of artists in urban regeneration processes and local development

Creativity plays a central role in driving both technological innovation and the development of creative products, serving as a fundamental input for these processes (Santagata, 2009). It also provides a competitive advantage when linked to culture and territory (Lazzeretti et al., 2012). This is particularly evident in urban environments, where creativity, combined with a cosmopolitan local identity (Cerisola and Panzera, 2022) and vibrant cultural participation, becomes a defining territorial asset. Historically, cities have been hubs of diverse cultures, education and talent, fostering talent generation, social vitality and cultural diversity (Zukin, 1995; Hall, 1998; Scott, 2000; UNESCO and World Bank, 2021). The urban environment is therefore an ideal setting to study the impact of creativity on social cohesion and economic growth, with artists playing a key role in urban regeneration as catalysts for creativity, vitality and community building.

Urban regeneration refers to the revitalization of neglected areas through cultural and artistic practices (Roberts, 2000), and artists are often at the heart of

this process. They give new life to these spaces, stimulate economic development, enhance aesthetic appeal and foster community (Murzyn-Kupisz and Działek, 2017). Increasingly, artists' contributions are understood through the framework of commoning practices, where informal, artist-led collectives collaborate to create cultural hubs anchored in shared values and connections (Borchi, 2018; Williams, 2018). These artists produce art and also engage in placemaking, enriching the socio-cultural fabric of the city (Wright, 2019). Their role in creative placemaking is particularly evident in contexts such as Rotterdam, where creative entrepreneurs contribute to sustainable tourism while also navigating the tensions between grassroots agency and city branding narratives (Nieuwland and Lavanga, 2021). This ambivalence reflects broader contradictions in the governance of cultural economies, where symbolic and community-driven work can be co-opted or displaced by market-oriented urban policies.

Artists are also central to the formation of cultural districts, understood as urban areas where artistic and creative activities cluster and interact with other sectors (Lavanga, 2020). These districts often emerge through bottom-up experimentation rather than top-down planning, revealing how informal artistic practices contribute to the evolution of cultural infrastructure and urban identity. Yet, as Lavanga (2020) and Rozentale and Lavanga (2014) have noted, the "universal" characteristics ascribed to creative industries risk ignoring the spatial and socio-political specificities of each city. Their work calls for more context-sensitive understandings of how creative practices evolve in relation to local governance, path dependencies, and urban imaginaries.

Accordingly, artists are increasingly recognized in the literature as entrepreneurs who challenge contemporary conventions and norms, often through innovative and disruptive artistic practices (Lindqvist, 2011). This entrepreneurial aspect is not limited to financial gain, but extends to improving social welfare and influencing the public agenda. Artists, like entrepreneurs, seek to innovate in their field, create new forms of expression and engage in cultural production that shapes societal values and drives public discourse (Morea and Dalla Chiesa, 2024). In this

context, the entrepreneurial nature of artists is evident in their ability to combine creativity with social engagement, often working to promote cultural participation, community building and social change. Lavanga and Schützle (2013) argue that social innovation in the arts cannot be driven by artists alone but requires structural support from institutions and intermediaries. Their work underscores the need for collaborative infrastructures that mediate between artistic experimentation and social utility, particularly in the context of urban transformation and cultural welfare.

These dynamics also resonate with the theories of the creative class (Florida, 2002) and the creative city (Pratt, 2008), which stress the importance of attracting creatives to drive economic growth and innovation. However, such theories have been widely critiqued for their instrumentalism and lack of attention to social justice. As Nieuwland, Lavanga, and Koens (2024) demonstrate in the case of Valencia, even when local governments rhetorically endorse sustainability and inclusion, grassroots efforts can be rendered ineffective by policy contradictions and bureaucratic inertia. Their study shows how bottom-up initiatives are not automatically emancipatory, especially when disconnected from meaningful institutional collaboration or when urban governance remains fragmented.

Indeed, artists' commitment goes beyond aesthetics; they act as agents of social change, strengthening community ties and contributing to the commons. Commoning practices in artist-led collectives can foster informal collaborative spaces that generate new forms of place-based knowledge (Wright, 2024). This contributes to both urban regeneration and the development of socio-cultural ecosystems (De Angelis and Harvie, 2014). Furthermore, these activities align with socially engaged art practices, where artists use their creativity to address local issues, build communities and encourage participation (Hope, 2017; Murzyn-Kupisz and Działek, 2017). As a result, artists' contributions in urban settings reflect broader cultural policy trends towards social inclusion and the empowerment of marginalized groups, while also influencing policy makers through grassroots cultural and political initiatives (Hope, 2017).

However, while these theories highlight the potential of art and creativity to stimulate urban development, they should not inform policies that view creativity in purely instrumental terms (Dekker and Morea, 2023). Rather than using arts and culture merely as tools to achieve economic and social outcomes, policies should focus on harnessing their intrinsic and plural values. Only by recognizing the affective, civic, and symbolic dimensions of cultural work can we fully account for the role that artists and independent spaces play in shaping more inclusive and resilient urban futures.

2.3 Independent art spaces in the urban context

A review of the literature revealed a scarcity of research on independent art spaces in cultural and economic studies, in comparison to urban studies. This approach may reflect the inadequacy of conventional categories in assessing these spaces (Blessi et al., 2011), as their operational models differ significantly from conventional commercial structures (Działek, 2021). Indeed, the multi-layered approach characteristic of urban studies is reflected in the diversity of definitions employed to describe these spaces, including art spaces, grassroots initiatives, informal practices, and more. The variety of terminology employed to describe them reflects the inherent complexity and non-commercial, often community-driven nature. Therefore, in order to analyze the organizational dynamics of independent art spaces, urban studies can provide useful tools and lenses.

Independent art spaces have been examined with greater focus on their relationship with the community than with the market (Lim et al., 2019; Lobo, 2018; Zilberstein, 2019; Działek, 2021; Gurney, 2023). This may be due to the fact that their market dynamics are markedly unconventional, being significantly detached from their commercial dynamics (Blessi et al., 2011; Działek, 2021). From an urban sociological perspective, an analysis of the relationship between these art spaces and the communities they serve is essential for understanding their role in urban social life. It is evident that these spaces are situated in close proximity to the urban

context and that they are inherently connected to the development of urban communities (Grodach, 2010; Gurney, 2023). The analysis of independent art spaces within urban studies indicates that their peripheral locations facilitate the detachment of these spaces from conventional market structures, thereby enabling them to become more closely integrated with the communities they serve (Malatjie, 2013; Lim et al., 2019). These spaces serve as public arenas where creative, political, and social practices contribute to the regeneration of urban spaces, particularly in industrial neighborhoods (Grodach, 2010; Gainza, 2018). The grassroots nature of these spaces further emphasizes their role in fostering robust connections with citizens and communities, which is pivotal from an urban sociological standpoint, as it pertains to processes of social cohesion and community development (Grodach, 2010; Sasajima, 2013; Zebracki, 2018; Morea and Sabatini, 2023).

The literature on art spaces within urban studies is complex and multi-layered, often employing different defining terms such as grassroots, informal, independent spaces and art spaces. In order to clarify this complexity, a more precise categorization is needed. Typically, art spaces are classified according to their purpose, including art co-operatives, art incubators, ethnic-specific art spaces, and community or cultural spaces. Each category serves a particular social function within the urban context. Art cooperatives foster collaboration, thereby aligning with theories of social capital and collective action (Putnam, 2000). Art incubators contribute to the social infrastructure necessary for cultural innovation (Klinenberg, 2018) by providing resources. Ethnic arts spaces reinforce cultural identity and diversity, which are key aspects of urban sociological studies on multiculturalism (Sandercock, 2003). Finally, community or cultural spaces serve as multifunctional hubs that strengthen local social networks and promote civic engagement (Grodach, 2011).

Further categorization enriches this analysis by taking into account the spatial locations, organizational structures and activities of the spaces in question (e.g. the categorization proposed Morea and Sabatini, 2023). This approach allows for a

more nuanced understanding of the different ways in which these spaces engage with their surrounding communities and urban environments. The diversity of formats and activities highlights the different contributions these spaces make to urban social life, and provides insights into their social and economic interactions. This classification covers both visual and performing arts and includes a variety of cultural organizations such as artists' collectives, cultural centers, research projects, networks, student collectives, artists' associations and social centers. Such a comprehensive mapping is particularly relevant to this study as it illustrates the richness of grassroots cultural practices and the diverse operational and definitional aspects of these spaces. Recognizing this diversity facilitates a more elaborated understanding of the different organizational models and activities that characterize alternative cultural spaces. In addition, this classification offers insights into the extent of their engagement with the market and the community, providing a clearer picture of their economic and social interactions.

Based on these categorizations, Figure 2.1 summarizes the classification of independent arts spaces, using their respective distance from the market and closeness to the community as criteria for classification. It is important to recognize the diversity and flexibility of these spaces when interpreting the diagram.³

³ Following the literature, it should be noted that the continuum shown in the figure does not imply that the closer spaces are to the art market, the more disconnected they are from communities. However, as these spaces move closer to the community on the continuum, they lose any relationship to the art market.

Furthermore, the figure does not take into account the relationship these spaces have with theatre and conventional performative arts, as this research only focuses on the visual contemporary art market. However, it is acknowledged here that most spaces also host performative arts (Morea and Sabatini, 2023), particularly given the increasing use of mixed media in contemporary art, especially in independent art spaces (Sharon, 1979).

occasionally intersect with market circuits (Blessi et al., 2011; Wright, 2019; Komarova, 2020). Their marginality within market studies reflects both their resistance to commodification and the limitations of dominant evaluative frameworks (Działek, 2021). Despite this, independent art spaces play a crucial role in sustaining cultural ecosystems through informal governance, care-based models, and relational forms of value creation (Jackson, 2004; Wright, 2024).

Urban studies have contributed further insights by focusing on the spatial and community-oriented dimensions of these initiatives. Scholars have demonstrated that their peripheral or interstitial urban locations foster detachment from market pressures and enable stronger connections with local communities (Grodach, 2010; Lim et al., 2019; Gurney, 2023). These spaces often act as grassroots infrastructures for social cohesion, civic participation, and cultural inclusion—particularly in contexts of post-industrial transition (Gainza, 2018; Morea and Sabatini, 2023). The multiplicity of labels—ranging from informal spaces to community art hubs—attests to the definitional and organizational heterogeneity of these initiatives. More recent typologies differentiate art cooperatives, incubators, ethnic art centers, and multifunctional spaces, each characterized by distinct relationships with the market and community (Grodach, 2011; Klinenberg, 2018; Sandercock, 2003). These classifications help map the complex ecology of contemporary cultural practices, where economic, political, and symbolic dynamics co-exist in fluid and sometimes contradictory ways. They also foreground the need for a more integrated analytical framework capable of capturing both the social embeddedness and the evolving organizational structures of these spaces.

Building on this body of research, this thesis defines independent art spaces as *artist-led initiatives that operate at the margins of the institutional art world and urban governance structures, often outside of formalized networks of funding, recognition, or evaluation*. These spaces are not solely defined by their lack of affiliation with market or public institutions, but by their capacity to generate autonomous and situated practices that priorities artistic experimentation, spatial reappropriation, and collective governance. In doing so, they blur the boundaries

between artistic labor, civic action, and community building. Independence is understood here as a dynamic and contextual condition that responds to specific socio-spatial constraints and opportunities while maintaining a commitment to non-instrumental, relational, and collaborative modes of production.

Indeed, artists' commitments extend well beyond aesthetics or economic productivity. They act as relational agents embedded in local contexts, whose practices contribute to forms of situated knowledge, spatial reappropriation, and community-making. In particular, commoning practices within artist-led collectives generate informal collaborative spaces that function as sites of experimentation and care (Wright, 2024). These practices do not simply "use" urban space—they redefine it, both materially and symbolically, thereby contributing to the regeneration of social and cultural ecologies (De Angelis and Harvie, 2014). This aligns with the literature on socially engaged art, which frames artistic interventions as embedded, dialogical, and community-responsive processes aimed at addressing local issues, fostering participation, and sustaining networks of mutual support (Hope, 2017; Murzyn-Kupisz and Działek, 2017).

These practices resonate with the evolving discourse in cultural policy toward inclusivity and empowerment, yet they simultaneously expose the limitations of policy regimes that remain tethered to output-based metrics and short-term programmatic funding. While grassroots cultural actors increasingly influence urban governance through relational and symbolic contributions, these remain undervalued in dominant evaluation systems. As argued by Dekker and Morea (2023), policies risk appropriating the language of creativity and participation while continuing to frame culture in service of external objectives—be they economic regeneration or social innovation—rather than acknowledging its intrinsic, affective, and communal value.

In this regard, there is a growing need to develop more expansive conceptual and analytical tools to grasp the complexity of these practices. Independent art spaces, in particular, challenge the dichotomies of formal/informal, public/private, and market/civic. They generate multiple and overlapping forms of value that are

not easily captured by existing models. This thesis responds to this gap by adopting the Value-Based Approach (VBA), which enables a more comprehensive understanding of the diverse value spheres at play in contemporary artistic production. The framework allows to articulate the significance of these practices not only in economic or cultural terms, but also in civic, social, personal, and even transcendental dimensions—setting the stage for the analytical framework developed in the following chapter.

Chapter 3

Rethinking value in cultural economics

How do we define and evaluate the value of artistic and cultural practices? This question underpins decades of interdisciplinary debate at the intersection of cultural economics, sociology, political theory, and cultural policy studies. From early attempts to justify public support for the arts through economic reasoning, to more recent efforts to recognize the intrinsic and relational dimensions of culture, scholars and policymakers alike have struggled to account for the complexity and plurality of values that cultural practices generate. Within the field of cultural economics, the foundational work of Baumol and Bowen (1966) and Throsby (2001) established a critical distinction between market value and cultural value, prompting attempts to measure non-market benefits through contingent valuation, cost-benefit analysis, and willingness-to-pay approaches. While such methods have been instrumental in legitimizing cultural expenditure within public finance frameworks, they rely on a logic of quantification that often fails to capture the lived, symbolic, and socially embedded nature of cultural experience. Moreover, these approaches assume a separation between economic and cultural logics, thereby overlooking the ways in which cultural practices negotiate and contest value across multiple domains of life.

More recent contributions from cultural sociology, urban studies, and critical policy analysis have attempted to move beyond these limitations by focusing on issues such as institutional logics, governance, and participation. Yet, as discussed in the previous chapter, much of this literature continues to frame artistic and cultural practices in terms of their social function or policy relevance, reinforcing an instrumental logic that obscures the multiplicity of values at play. This is

particularly problematic when examining independent and artist-led spaces, which often operate outside institutional norms and generate forms of value that are fluid, informal, and grounded in specific places, relationships, and modes of co-creation.

To respond to these challenges, this chapter introduces the VBA, developed by Klamer (2016), as an alternative theoretical lens that places value at the center of inquiry—not as a singular or measurable outcome, but as a plural and situated process embedded in social interaction. By conceptualizing value through five overlapping spheres—market, government, social, personal, and transcendental—the VBA enables a more comprehensive understanding of how cultural practices are valued by different actors, in different settings, and for different reasons. This framework is particularly well suited to studying independent art spaces, where artistic, social, political, and personal motivations often co-exist and where practices unfold through contingent, relational dynamics.

This chapter critically reviews the evolution of valuation frameworks in cultural economics and presents the VBA as a suitable analytical approach for capturing the complexity of value in grassroots cultural practices. The chapter is structured as follows: Section 3.2 examines conventional models in cultural economics, highlighting their achievements and limits. Section 3.3 compares the VBA to other conceptual frameworks in cultural and urban studies, showing how it addresses key gaps. Section 3.4 explores the theoretical foundations of the VBA. Section 3.5 introduces the five spheres of value in detail, and Section 3.6 outlines how this approach will be operationalized in the empirical analysis that follows.

3.1 The origins of cultural economics

The theory that marked the beginning of cultural economics was first articulated by Baumol and Bowen (1966) and subsequently elaborated by Peacock (1969), Throsby and Withers (1979). They argue that the arts represent a case of market failure and advocate public support for culture and the arts. This approach remains a fundamental principle of efficiency-based arguments (Throsby, 2003, p. 276) and

has been instrumental in shaping the conceptualization of the cultural good within the field of cultural economics. Consequently, the arts and culture have been subjected to analysis as industries, with the application of economic concepts to facilitate an understanding of the sector's dynamics. According to this perspective, terms such as "industry," "cultural district," "commons," "externality," and "long-term investment" have become, and in most cases remain, the primary focus of cultural economic studies (Peacock, 1994; Bille Hansen, 1995; Pratt, 1997; Santagata, 2002; Throsby, 2008; Bertacchini et al., 2012).

Notwithstanding the theoretical development of cultural economics towards a market-centered understanding, aimed at 'saving' culture by substantiating its relevance, the theory of market failure persists in assuming the enduring importance and existence of symbolic and cultural values in cultural goods, which define them beyond their economic value (Bàrrere and Santagata, 1999; Throsby, 2001). It is thus acknowledged that the cultural good possesses a dual value, namely economic and cultural. Nevertheless, the assessment of cultural value remains a topic of discussion in the field (Angelini and Castellani, 2019).

In this context, it is important to clarify that non-market values are not synonymous with cultural value. As Throsby (2001) observes, "while economic value encompasses all the direct use values of the cultural good or service in question, in addition to any non-market values it may generate, cultural value is multidimensional, unstable, contested, lacks a common unit of account, and may contain elements that cannot be easily expressed on any quantitative or qualitative scale" (pp. 279-280). In this sense, cultural economists are well-positioned to capture economic value, encompassing both market and non-market values (Throsby, 2001; De la Torre, 2002; Klamer, 2003). Some scholars have begun to question the appropriateness of evaluating non-market values alone for the purposes of exploring, analyzing and measuring culture, and for informing cultural policy. One line of argument argues that the theory of market failure was shaped by specific contextual factors, namely budgetary constraints and the imperative for the public sector, and for the arts and culture in particular, to substantiate its economic

relevance (Throsby, 2003; Klamer, 2004; Trimarchi, 2004). Furthermore, scholars have documented instances where politicians, artists, and other stakeholders have asserted that the value of the arts cannot be quantified in monetary terms, particularly due to the existence of cultural values associated with it (Throsby, 2001; Throsby, 2003). Accordingly, the emphasis on economic value has largely informed the theoretical discourse on cultural economics, influencing the development of evaluation methodologies. For instance, Bonus and Ronte (1997) argue that economic value is inherently encompassed by cultural value. Other researchers, such as Throsby (2001) and Hutter and Frey (2010), put forth the view that cultural value exerts an influence on economic value, while nevertheless maintaining that the two remain distinct. Accordingly, a cultural economist does not typically assess a painting in terms of its cultural value, as this is the domain of the art critic, the curator, or perhaps the dealer (Seaman, 2006).

The emphasis on measuring economic value has resulted in the frequent utilization of contingent valuation techniques, which employ surveys to ascertain individuals' willingness to pay for hypothetical alterations to a good or service (Noonan, 2003). Such applications have included studies of demand for the public goods provided by cultural institutions, such as theatres (Bille Hansen, 1997) and museums (Martin, 1994; Santagata and Signorello, 2000), as well as projects to restore or preserve cultural heritage buildings and sites (e.g. Mourato et al., 2002; Cuccia and Signorello, 2000; Pollicino and Maddison, 2001). Moreover, they encompass evaluations of the willingness to pay for pure public goods within the cultural sector, such as free-to-air television programs (Papandrea, 1999). For further overviews, see Pagiola (1996), Bille Hansen et al. (1998), Navrud and Ready (2002) and Noonan (2003).

In the last two decades, however, an increasing number of scholars have proposed that an evaluation that considers only the economic value, including market and non-market values, is incomplete without accounting for the cultural value of the artistic and cultural good. This is because art and culture are exceptional goods, and it is crucial to differentiate them from other goods (Throsby, 2000, 2001,

2003; Klamer, 2003; Trimarchi, 2004; Throsby and Zednik, 2014; Klamer, 2016, 2017; Klamer et al., 2022). This prompts the question of whether this is a task for the cultural economist. This is undoubtedly the case. It is evident that measuring economic value alone will never provide the policy maker with a complete picture from which to choose between two projects to fund. It is therefore imperative for cultural economists to consider this matter if they are to inform policy and influence the development of the market for ideas (which determines the cultural price of the good) beyond the market for the good (which determines the economic price) (Throsby, 2003).

3.2 The value-based approach to cultural economics

In his major study on the value of culture, Throsby assesses the feasibility of analyzing the arts as an industry and its economic and social value (2001). This raises critical questions about the reliability of modern economic tools for studying this relationship (Klamer, 1997). An over-emphasis on economic approaches may risk reducing culture and the arts to mere instruments of social cohesion and economic growth, sidelining their intrinsic value (Belfiore, 2004; Angelini and Castellani, 2019). In light of these concerns, the aim of this second section is to explore Klamer's proposal for a value-based approach to cultural economics, which emphasizes the incorporation of cultural and artistic valorization (2016). Klamer defines the process of artistic or cultural valorization as the attribution of artistic and cultural significance to a given work. This process is an important aspect of the artist's everyday practice and is highly emphasized by cultural professionals such as art critics and art historians. However, it is often overlooked by economists. By addressing this shortcoming, Klamer's approach argues for a more holistic understanding of the value of the arts, one that transcends purely economic metrics and recognizes the multifaceted significance of cultural contributions. This perspective is crucial for developing policies that appreciate the intrinsic value of

the arts and foster a more nuanced dialogue between economic analysis and cultural significance.

3.2.1 About values and their articulation

In relation to the formulation of the concept of cultural value, Klamer (2003) challenges the economic perspective of supporting culture, which is characterized by an instrumental view of culture. Moreover, he draws a clear line between the approaches of economists and those of cultural experts, emphasizing the differences between the two groups. The former group of scholars critique cultural experts for their failure to acknowledge the economic aspects of cultural heritage, while the latter group of scholars argue that economists fail to recognize the unique value of culture. Additionally, Klamer notes that in public discourse, the former perspective is gaining ground over the latter. This is evidenced by the growing tendency of politicians and bureaucrats to rely on economic valuations in order to justify public expenditure on culture and the arts. This approach is proving inadequate and insufficient, with studies increasingly demonstrating its relevance (Belfiore, 2002; Angelini and Castellani, 2019; Petrova et al., 2022; Klamer et al., 2022).

The cultural field is a complex entity, and economic schemes seek to simplify it in order to enhance the viability of arts and cultural organizations. This approach may prove beneficial in the short term, when funds are allocated by government or local foundations. Nevertheless, in the long term, it may result in significant losses of value. In light of the aforementioned considerations, Klamer puts forth an approach that prioritizes values. The VBA postulates the significance of social and cultural values. However, the tendency to conceptualize the field in quantitative terms, through systems and models, risks overlooking the qualitative sphere, which is integral to understanding the field's inherent complexity. This qualitative aspect cannot be disregarded (Klamer, 2017; Petrova et al., 2022). It is not the intention of the VBA to displace cultural economics or the role of the economist. Conversely, its objective is to reinforce the academic field and associated practices in order to encompass all spheres and values inherent to cultural practice (Klamer, 2004). It is

the social and cultural milieu that culture and the arts enhance; economic concepts are inadequate for capturing the value created in these spheres.

In this sense, valorization differs from evaluation. Both are forms of evaluation, but the first entails the generation of value around the object in question, whereas the second is the assessment of a pre-established value based on specific criteria. VBA proposes the use of the latter to encapsulate cultural and social value (Klamer, 2017), which is then operationalized through the application of the five-sphere model (Petrova et al., 2022; Klamer et al., 2022). This will be discussed in greater detail subsequently. The process of valorization allows for the development of new indicators beyond the standard ones, thus facilitating a more nuanced exploration of the nature of what Klamer defines as common or social goods (2017).

Given these premises, Klamer puts forth the proposition that values manifest in a multitude of facets of life, extending beyond the domain of individual values (2017). The question of what is important is answered by values, which reveal cultural distinctions. In his 2001 study, Throsby identifies six values associated with cultural goods, namely aesthetic, spiritual, symbolic, social, and authenticity. However, the analysis of Klamer expands this to include personal values and clusters values into four dimensions. Personal values are those that pertain to one's relationship with the self. Such values may include, for instance, those pertaining to health, autonomy, and personal growth. By way of illustration, personal values may encompass one's abilities or the personal import of Shakespeare's dramatic works. Social values are formed through relationships with known individuals, including those in one's social circle, such as friends, family, and members of one's community. For instance, special branded shoes are perceived as a marker of social status, whereas attending a theatrical performance with friends is an activity that fosters social bonding. Social values are derived from relationships with known individuals, including those within one's social circle, such as friends, family, and members of one's community. The category of transcendental or cultural values is distinguished by an emphasis on abstract ideals and practices that transcend the personal, social, and societal realms. Such values encompass historical, artistic, and

moral considerations. For instance, Shakespeare's oeuvre is of historical, artistic, and moral significance, addressing themes such as loyalty and love.

3.2.2 Five-spheres model

The clustering of values permits a more comprehensive understanding of their applicability across a range of contexts, from the personal to the societal and cultural. The VBA is predicated on the recognition of the existence of multiple values (Klamer 1997; Throsby 2001; Hutter 2011) and the construction of a conceptual framework for the valuation of cultural goods, which is known as the five-sphere model. The model is based on the concept of valorization, which can be defined as the process of realizing the value of goods, services or ideas by involving others in their recognition and exchange. The process of valorization is inherently social, as it necessitates the involvement of individuals capable of recognizing and exchanging value. The model is structured in a manner that is contrary to the conventional economic perspective, which primarily focuses on markets and government as the primary means of valorization. In this view, markets function through the mechanism of price, while governments provide public goods and intervene when markets are unable to function effectively. However, this standard model is limited in that it does not take into account the ways in which people realize non-economic values, such as friendship, trust, or achievements in the arts and sciences.

Figure 3.1. The five-sphere model. Source: Klamer (2017).

In order to address these limitations, the model proposed by Klamer (2017) suggests a more comprehensive framework that includes additional spheres of valorization beyond the market and government. The initial sphere of consideration is the social sphere (S), which encompasses networks and relationships in which individuals engage in the sharing and discussion of their work, thereby gaining recognition and support. This sphere is of particular importance for artists, academics and others whose work is dependent upon the engagement and appreciation of their peers and audiences. A further sphere is that of the cultural or artistic sphere (C), which encompasses the distinctive discourses and practices that characterize artistic or academic communities. In these contexts, value is realized through the utilization of shared terminology, values and codes that define what is considered innovative, political, interdisciplinary or authentic. This sphere is of particular importance for the artist in question, who engages with students and government officials in order to gain recognition and support for his project. The *oikos* (O), or domestic sphere, also plays a pivotal role in the valorization process. The family and the domestic environment provide a supportive and valuing context for an individual's work, offering both emotional and practical assistance. Such support is of particular importance to the artist, who depends on the understanding and sacrifices of his family in order to pursue his artistic endeavors. In order to illustrate the manner in which valorization efforts span multiple spheres, including the social, cultural, and *oikos* spheres, Klamer presents the example of an artist working on a project to explore cities in a novel manner. Subsequently, the artist encounters obstacles in the market (M) and government (G) spheres, underscoring the necessity for identifying and engaging potential supporters or purchasers.

3.3 Why a value-based approach? Comparing with existing frameworks

Over the past decades, several theoretical approaches have shaped our understanding of value in the cultural field. Foundational work within cultural economics, particularly that of Baumol and Bowen (1966), Peacock (1969), and Throsby (2001), has emphasized the problem of market failure in the arts. These models argue for public support based on the notion that cultural production, due to its specific cost structures and public good characteristics, cannot be sustained through market mechanisms alone. While influential in policy debates, such approaches tend to treat value as something measurable—typically through tools such as willingness to pay, cost-benefit analysis, or contingent valuation. As a result, they privilege economic efficiency over the lived, symbolic, or relational dimensions that often define artistic practices, particularly in informal or non-commercial contexts.

A second set of perspectives emerges from cultural policy studies, especially in the context of urban development and creative city strategies. Scholars have interrogated the strategic use of culture in fostering regeneration, inclusion, and innovation (Landry and Bianchini, 1995; Belfiore, 2004). Yet, by framing culture primarily as a tool for economic or social outcomes, these accounts often adopt an instrumental logic. They tend to focus on what culture does for society, rather than on how cultural actors themselves define and generate value through everyday practices.

Together, these frameworks have shaped an interdisciplinary understanding of cultural value, but they remain limited in capturing the full spectrum of values at stake in independent art practices—particularly those that are informal, collaborative, or oriented toward civil society rather than the market. This is where the Value-Based Approach (Klamer, 2016, 2017) offers a compelling alternative. In his framework, values and evaluation are treated as grounded in social interaction, cultural context, and shared meaning-making. The analytical strength

of the VBA lies in the recognition that cultural practices are embedded in multiple value spheres simultaneously: the market (exchange), the state (policy and regulation), the social (community and relationships), the personal (identity and aspiration), and the transcendental (ideals, beauty, purpose). This pluralistic approach enables a more comprehensive understanding of how value is created, negotiated, and sustained within independent art spaces, which often function through collective use, informal governance, and context-specific dynamics. . Moreover, it raises the broader question of whether independent artists, often operating outside formal structures, are increasingly becoming part of civil society and co-producing public goods through cultural means (Klamer, 2017; Klamer et al., 2022; Petrova et al., 2022).

Chapter 4

Generating values in independent art spaces: A framework for analysis

This chapter introduces the analytical framework through which the empirical material of this research will be interpreted. Drawing on the Value-Based Approach (VBA) outlined in Chapter 3, it develops a set of conceptual tools tailored to the study of independent art spaces operating outside conventional market and institutional frameworks. The chapter builds on insights from the literature review and repositions the analysis of grassroots artistic practices within a broader understanding of value as plural, situated, and socially embedded. It is structured as follows: Section 4.1 outlines the operationalization of the VBA in the context of the selected case study, describing how each of the five value spheres will be identified and traced. Section 4.2 draws conclusions from the literature and defines the premises for the empirical investigation. Section 4.3 reflects on how values are articulated and negotiated in the evolving art market, proposing a model of valorization that foregrounds the diversity and interdependence of value spheres in contemporary artistic practices.

4.1 Operationalizing the value-based approach for independent art spaces

The Value-Based Approach (VBA) offers a theoretical perspective from which to reflect on cultural value and also functions as an analytical framework to guide empirical inquiry. In the context of this research, the five value spheres outlined by

Klamer (2016) serve as heuristic categories through which to interpret how value is produced, expressed, and mobilized within the everyday practices of Associazione Bastione. Rather than being treated as rigid typologies, these spheres operate as interpretative devices that allow for the recognition of overlapping, relational, and evolving forms of value that characterize grassroots artistic initiatives.

Methodologically, the research draws on qualitative materials collected through semi-structured interviews, participant observation, and fieldnotes. These sources are examined to trace the situated narratives and practices through which actors articulate their motivations, negotiate tensions, and generate value in relation to their artistic, organizational, and spatial environments. Each value sphere informs a distinct but interconnected dimension of the analysis.

The market sphere captures how economic concerns are navigated—such as access to resources, forms of exchange, or sustainability strategies—often within contexts of scarcity and informality. The government sphere considers how actors interact with public authorities, institutional frameworks, and regulatory constraints, as well as how they position themselves vis-à-vis dominant cultural policies. The social sphere refers to the collaborative dynamics, affective bonds, and informal networks that sustain the collective dimension of practice. The personal sphere encompasses individual aspirations, trajectories, and forms of self-realization that underpin involvement in such initiatives. Finally, the transcendental sphere speaks to the invocation of broader ideals—such as autonomy, justice, or artistic integrity—that exceed the pragmatic and enter the realm of values that guide action over time.

Through the empirical application of the VBA, this research aims to foreground the multiplicity of value regimes at play in independent art spaces, and to highlight how these regimes are embedded in context-specific forms of governance, spatial use, and cultural labor. This approach offers a way to reframe the analysis of artistic practices beyond dominant logics of measurement, visibility, or institutional categorization, and sets the foundation for the methodological articulation developed in the following chapter.

4.2 Conclusions from the literature review and premises for the empirical analysis

The literature review has illuminated key trajectories in the evolution of both the contemporary art market and the development of independent art spaces. While formal market structures—such as galleries, fairs, and institutional networks—appear slow to adapt to shifting artistic paradigms, independent art spaces have emerged as agile, situated responses to evolving socio-cultural and spatial conditions. Initially associated with the politically driven countercultures of the 1960s and 1970s, these spaces have progressively redefined their role, placing increasing emphasis on the search for autonomy, community, and embeddedness. Rather than forming as anomalies on the periphery of the art world, they represent grounded and iterative forms of cultural production shaped by specific contexts, spatial constraints, and shared values.

In particular, the literature has pointed to the growing entanglement between independent artistic practices and urban transformation processes. As cities across Europe increasingly seek to reimagine former industrial infrastructures and underutilised public buildings, independent art spaces frequently intervene in these transitional landscapes—not merely as users of space, but as co-producers of meaning, care, and social infrastructure. Their presence often anticipates or accompanies broader dynamics of urban regeneration, while simultaneously contesting the logics of commodification and institutionalisation that frequently accompany them. These trajectories raise important questions about how such spaces redefine artistic practice in relation to broader socio-spatial configurations. Against this background, the present research addresses the following overarching question:

How do grassroots artistic practices reshape the boundaries between the market, the public sector, and the civil sphere in contemporary cultural production?

This is explored through the following sub-questions:

In what ways do independent art spaces organize cultural production through collective use, co-creation, and situated governance?

How do these practices generate and negotiate value(s) that escape conventional economic or policy-driven evaluative frameworks?

What contextual conditions (urban, social, political) enable or constrain these alternative modes of cultural production?

Linking the insights from Chapters 1 and 2 with the conceptual apparatus introduced in Chapter 3, this chapter provides the premises for the operationalization of the Value-Based Approach (VBA) in the context of empirical analysis. The review has shown that dominant approaches—particularly those grounded in economic evaluation or policy-oriented metrics—often fall short in accounting for the plurality of values generated by informal and grassroots cultural practices. While sociological and urban studies literature has contributed valuable perspectives on institutional dynamics, governance, and legitimacy, it often lacks a sufficiently articulated framework to capture the lived, affective, and transcendent dimensions of cultural value. The VBA, as developed by Klamer (2016), offers an alternative framework that foregrounds value as a situated, dialogical, and plural process, enacted across distinct but interrelated spheres.

The analytical strength of this framework lies in its capacity to recognize how cultural actors operate simultaneously within, across, and sometimes in tension with, five spheres of value: the market, the state, the social, the personal, and the transcendental. This enables a more comprehensive account of the complexity of independent artistic practices, without reducing them to economic functions, policy outcomes, or aesthetic categories. In this sense, the VBA aligns with the broader epistemological commitment of this research: to develop an interpretative and relational approach to value that is attuned to the specificity of place, practice, and community. The empirical investigation focuses on Associazione Bastione, an independent artist-led collective based in Turin. The group currently comprises ten artists and operates as a formally recognized non-profit organization. Its roots lie in the self-organized occupation of the Cavallerizza Reale complex—a historic urban

site in the heart of Turin—which functioned for several years as a space of cultural experimentation, political negotiation, and informal artistic production. The transition from an informal occupation to a recognized association reflects broader dynamics observed in many European cities, where grassroots initiatives oscillate between autonomy and institutionalization, often navigating ambiguous relations with public authorities and regulatory frameworks.

The selection of this case study is grounded in a number of considerations. Turin offers a historically layered cultural context—ranging from its role in the emergence of *Arte Povera* to its current institutional ecology, which includes *Artissima* and *Castello di Rivoli*. *Associazione Bastione*'s position within this landscape makes it a compelling lens through which to examine how independent art spaces engage with, resist, or reconfigure dominant value systems. In addition, the group's consistent involvement in processes of spatial transformation—particularly in relation to green urban areas and public buildings—reveals the extent to which artistic practices are also spatial and political interventions. On at least two occasions, the group attempted to reclaim and reimagine urban gardens as sites of creative practice, yet in both cases they encountered institutional obstacles that eventually led to conflict or displacement. These episodes are indicative of broader tensions between grassroots experimentation and bureaucratic logics, and speak to the need for new interpretative frameworks to understand how value is created, recognized, or marginalized in such contexts.

In this regard, the case of *Associazione Bastione* offers a situated and generative perspective on the value dynamics at play in independent art spaces. Through the empirical application of the VBA, this research aims to generate knowledge that can be extended to other contexts—both as an analytical framework and as a set of reflections on the changing conditions of artistic autonomy, cultural production, and urban transformation. The case also holds relevance for cultural policy and urban governance, particularly in relation to public space management, informal infrastructure, and the role of artistic practices in reimagining collective life in cities.

4.3 About values and their articulation for a valorization in the evolving art market: A value based approach

The VBA offers a comprehensive framework for analyzing the plural values generated through cultural production, extending beyond purely financial or policy-driven metrics. This chapter builds on existing scholarship on the VBA (Klamer et al., 2022; Petrova et al., 2022) to develop an analytical model tailored to independent art spaces. In doing so, it seeks to address a critical gap in both academic literature and cultural policy: the persistent neglect of contextual, social, and symbolic values in favor of market-based indicators. While independent art spaces operate at the margins of the formal art market, they play a central role in shaping new forms of cultural engagement and urban transformation. The aim of this chapter is therefore to articulate a framework that captures the multiple dimensions of value embedded in these practices.

Specifically, the chapter explores how independent art spaces are positioned between artistic autonomy and institutional dependency, and how they generate value across a range of domains—economic, political, social, personal, and transcendental. The guiding: *Why is it necessary to construct a value framework capable of accounting for the environments in which independent artists and collectives operate?* The rationale lies in the observation that dominant frameworks tend to privilege financial metrics while underrepresenting the situated, relational, and experimental aspects of contemporary artistic practice.

Figure 4.1 provides a conceptual entry point by highlighting key domains of value—transcendental, societal, personal, and social—commonly associated with independent art spaces. These dimensions serve as a heuristic for developing a more grounded application of the VBA, which will be discussed in the following sections.

Figure 4.1 About values and their articulation in independent art spaces, according to the literature. Source: author's own elaboration.

Drawing on literature on the VBA (Klamer 2016; 2017), the diagram highlights five domains: Transcendental, Societal, Social, Personal and Experimental. These categories foreground values that are often overlooked by conventional cultural economic frameworks. For instance, transcendental values refer to the experimental nature of artistic practice; societal values relate to the role of artists in raising political and social awareness; social values center around friendship and informal bonds; and personal values concern the pursuit of independence—both ideologically and financially. Together, these categories provide an entry point for a more comprehensive analysis of how value is generated and sustained in grassroots artistic contexts.

To enable a structured and empirically grounded analysis, this model is here reinterpreted through the lens of the VBA, which identifies five overlapping spheres of value: market, government, social, personal, and transcendental. The application of this framework to the case of Associazione Bastione allows us to trace how value is articulated in relation to different actors, systems, and motivations. What follows is a reclassification of the values introduced above, with each sphere illustrated by

existing literature and followed by reflections on how it might emerge in the Bastione case.

Market value refers to how artistic and organizational practices intersect with economic systems and logics. While independent art spaces often position themselves as alternatives to the commercial art market, they are not entirely outside of it. Market value may surface in their engagement with artist residencies, fundraising efforts, ticketed events, or occasional sales of artworks (Działek, 2021; Blessi et al., 2011). In the case of Bastione, market value might emerge through strategies that seek to ensure financial sustainability without compromising artistic autonomy—for example, selective collaborations with festivals or applications for project-based cultural grants.

Government value captures the relationship between independent cultural practices and public institutions. These interactions include legal recognition, access to public spaces, and the negotiation of funding streams. While many independent spaces operate as non-profits, they remain embedded in regulatory frameworks that can both enable and constrain their work (Jackson, 2004). For Bastione, government value might be observed in the group's attempts to engage municipal authorities in discussions around the use of green urban areas—efforts that have sometimes led to tensions, especially in the aftermath of their eviction from Cavallerizza. Their navigation of public policy frameworks reflects wider dynamics of institutional dependence, negotiation, and resistance.

Social value encompasses both societal and interpersonal dimensions. On one level, these spaces contribute to broader societal goals by fostering political awareness, encouraging participation, and activating underused urban areas (Grodach, 2010; Murzyn-Kupisz and Działek, 2017; Hope, 2017). On another level, they operate as relational ecosystems where collaboration is grounded in friendship and mutual support rather than institutional hierarchy (Wright, 2019; Wright, 2024). In Bastione's case, social value might manifest in the group's commitment to collective governance, shared authorship, and informal peer learning. Their artistic

practice is embedded in the social fabric of the neighborhood, contributing to processes of urban regeneration while maintaining strong local ties.

Personal value relates to the motivations, ideologies, and aspirations of individual artists. Independent art spaces often enable forms of self-realization that escape the constraints of institutional or market logics (Sharon, 1979; Jackson, 2004). Personal value might involve artistic autonomy, political alignment, or a rejection of standardized career trajectories. Within Bastione, personal value might be articulated in members' decisions to remain independent, their resistance to professionalization, or their shared investment in forms of slow, situated artistic production that reflect individual and collective visions.

Transcendental value refers to higher-order principles that drive creative work, including the pursuit of truth, aesthetic innovation, and ethical engagement (Klamer, 2017; Chun, 2016; Grodach, 2010). These values are often difficult to quantify but are central to how artists understand the purpose and role of their work. In independent art spaces, transcendental value might be expressed through a commitment to experimentation, the disruption of conventional artistic forms, or the symbolic reclaiming of space. In Bastione's case, this could be observed in the group's insistence on reimagining public spaces not just functionally, but poetically and politically—transforming gardens and former industrial buildings into laboratories of shared meaning. Table 4.1 presents a summary of the interpretation of the VBA in the context of independent art spaces.

Value Sphere	Definition	Relevant literature
Market	Engagement with economic systems, sustainability strategies, and financial autonomy.	Działek, 2021; Blessi et al., 2011
Government	Interaction with public institutions, including legal frameworks, access to public space, and public funding.	Jackson, 2004

Value Sphere	Definition	Relevant literature
Social	Relational and communal dynamics, including collaboration, co-creation, and urban social regeneration.	Grodach, 2010; Hope, 2017; Wright, 2019; Wright, 2024
Personal	Individual aspirations, identity, autonomy, and ideological motivations of artists.	Sharon, 1979; Jackson, 2004
Transcendental	Pursuit of higher-order values: truth, beauty, symbolic meaning, and ethical experimentation.	Chun, 2016; Grodach, 2010

Table 4.1 Interpretation of the VBA in the context of independent art spaces and relevant literature.

Chapter 5

Methodology

5.1 Research design

The central research question guiding this research is: How do independent art spaces reshape the boundaries between the market, the public sector, and the civil sphere in contemporary cultural production?

This question is explored through the following sub-questions:

1. In what ways do independent art spaces organize cultural production through collective use, co-creation, and situated governance?
2. How do these practices generate and negotiate value(s) that escape conventional economic or policy-driven evaluative frameworks?
3. What contextual conditions (urban, social, political) enable or constrain these alternative modes of cultural production?

To answer these questions, this study adopts an in-depth single-case study methodology focused on Associazione Bastione, an independent art space in Turin, Italy. The case study method enables detailed exploration of complex, situated phenomena at the intersection of artistic experimentation, collective organisation, and urban transformation. Associazione Bastione's evolution—from occupation of the historic Cavallerizza complex to formal non-profit status—provides a paradigmatic context to investigate how independent art spaces challenge and reconfigure conventional cultural, economic, and institutional boundaries.

As highlighted by Simons (2014), the case study approach offers a comprehensive means to investigate a phenomenon within its natural context,

especially when the phenomenon and context are deeply intertwined. This approach allows for deep data collection and analysis, enabling insights into broader theoretical and practical questions.

This research follows an abductive research logic (Timmermans & Tavory, 2012), whereby theory and empirical observation interact iteratively. The Value-Based Approach (VBA), developed in Chapter 4, provided an initial conceptual framework that was both applied to and refined by the empirical work. This abductive process shaped the design of research instruments and informed the analytical coding, allowing for emergent themes that expanded beyond initial theoretical assumptions.

The research unfolded over four interconnected phases, depicted in Figure 5.1. The first phase comprised a literature review and the development of the conceptual framework centered on value production in independent art spaces. The second phase involved mapping the artistic ecosystem of Turin and selecting the case study. The third and most extensive phase consisted of empirical fieldwork, including semi-structured interviews, participant observation, and document analysis. The final phase focused on data synthesis and interpretation in light of the evolving VBA framework.

Figure 5.1. The four phases of the research design. Source: author's own elaboration.

Methodologically, the study combined deductive and inductive strategies. A deductive approach informed the initial development of interview protocols and observation guidelines based on existing literature and the VBA framework. Subsequently, an inductive approach was employed in data coding and analysis, allowing novel categories and patterns to emerge from the empirical material. This combination ensured methodological rigour while maintaining openness to the complex realities of grassroots cultural production (Newman, 2000).

The abductive and iterative design enabled the research to capture the plural, situated and evolving nature of value generation in independent art spaces. The case of Associazione Bastione offered insights into how artistic autonomy, collective governance, and urban embeddedness interact under contemporary cultural and socio-political conditions.

5.2 Data collection

The data collection process was complex and iterative, reflecting the often messy reality of qualitative research. The approach was abductive, simultaneously drawing on deductive preparation and inductive responsiveness. This allowed the research to evolve organically, adapting methods and focus in response to what was encountered in the field. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and participant observation, as summarized in Table 5.1.

	Semistructured interviews	Participant observation
Participants	10	19
Total hours	14	60
Total words	85.651 words transcriptions	20.348 words notes

Table 5.1. Data collected. Source: author's own elaboration.

The interview guide was initially developed deductively, informed by the Value-Based Approach (VBA) framework presented in Chapter 4. It provided a flexible guide to explore key themes such as artistic practice, governance, and economic strategies. However, the questions and focus shifted throughout the process as new insights emerged, leading to the refinement of the guide and the emergence of unanticipated topics.

Semi-structured interviews with the ten artists who run Associazione Bastione lasted between one and one and a half hours each (based on the guide in figure 5.2). These conversations were often open-ended and exploratory, allowing participants to discuss their personal experiences and collective visions in depth. The interview process was about engaging in a dialogue that shaped both the data and the researcher's understanding.

Participant observation was conducted over six months (January to June 2024), focusing on the collective's weekly meetings and activities. This hands-on involvement included both online and face-to-face sessions, as well as participation in the preparation of funding applications and interactions with guest artists at informal gatherings (i.e. collective lunches). Observing these processes firsthand was crucial for understanding the internal dynamics, informal interactions, and everyday practices that inform the artists' work.

Throughout the research, data collection was shaped by ongoing reflection and adaptation. The process was complex and surprising, as studying an artistic collective in progress is inevitably going to be. Detailed fieldnotes and reflective memos documented ongoing events and the contextual factors influencing the group's practices. This hands-on, flexible approach to data collection was essential for capturing the evolving and situated practice of Associazione Bastione.

Figure 5.2. Interview guide. Source: author's own elaboration

5.3 Data analysis

Data analysis was conducted through thematic analysis using the qualitative data analysis software Atlas.ti. The process was iterative and flexible, beginning with an initial round of coding on interview transcripts and observation notes to identify recurring patterns and categories. The coding was initially guided by the conceptual framework developed in Chapter 4, which provided a useful structure for focusing on relevant value spheres. At the same time, the analysis remained open to new and unexpected themes emerging from the data. Codes were grouped into categories, which were then organized into broader themes reflecting key dimensions of the research questions. This thematic structuring involved continual reflection, comparison, and refinement to ensure that the categories captured the complexity of Associazione Bastione’s practices. The framework guided the analysis systematically, revealing how the collective engages with the art market, the public sector, and the community. This approach ensured coherence and depth and also allowed the data to challenge and expand theoretical assumptions. Table 5.2 presents an overview of the main themes and categories identified through this process, illustrating how the analysis connected empirical observations with the theoretical concerns of the study.

Codes	Categories	Themes
Experimentation, Cross-fertilisation	Artistic identity	Redefining the way artists make art, network and build careers
Lack of space	Co-creation	
Professional roles, Autonomy in work	Definition	
Community	Exhibiting format	

Use of space, Artistic roles	Role of physical space in artistic practices	Caring for the space as a home where communities are built through hospitality and co-creation
Renovation, Maintenance	Role of physical space in artistic practices	
Interaction with local community, Shared spaces	Community engagement	
Collaboration with local institutions, Schools, Partnerships	Community engagement and external relations	
Interaction with local community	Community engagement	
Resource management, Financial sustainability	Costs and benefits	Maintaining artistic autonomy, seeking dialogue with the government and facing institutional voids
Non-economy, Sharing skills	Horizontal organization	
Personal vs. group identity, Financial sustainability	Artistic identity and financial sustainability	

Table 5.2. A restitution of the codes, categories and themes identified through the thematic analysis.

Thematic analysis, as outlined by Clarke and Braun (2021), proves useful in this context. Reflexive thematic analysis is particularly suited to qualitative research, where the aim is to uncover and interpret patterns within the data. Clarke and Braun (2021) argue that thematic analysis allows for flexibility in data interpretation, allowing for the exploration and articulation of complexities and themes that emerge from the data. This approach is beneficial for capturing the dynamics of an independent arts center such as Associazione Bastione, where themes related to community engagement, management and artistic collaboration are interconnected. Specifically, reflexive thematic analysis involves an ongoing engagement with the data and the researcher's own perspectives, allowing for a deeper, more reflexive understanding of the themes that emerge (Braun and Clarke, 2019). In this case, reflexivity allowed the elaboration of the codes and their re-elaboration to be aligned with the established frameworks (Figure 4.2 and Figure 4.3). This resulted

in the identification of themes that reflected the overarching framework and ultimately informed the formulation of the general conclusions presented in Chapter 8. In this case, the approach was instrumental in ensuring that the analysis was rigorous and responsive to the insights gained through participant observation and interviews. The focus on themes after identifying categories enabled a comprehensive overview of Associazione Bastione's organizational dynamics. Overall, thematic reflexive analysis provided a robust framework for interpreting the complex data gathered through the research methods.

Reflexive thematic analysis was crucial in understanding all aspects of the dynamics of an independent art centers. In particular, it helped to identify patterns and themes in order to organize and interpret qualitative data to uncover recurring themes or patterns. In the study of Associazione Bastione, contextualizing the data helped to see how different elements of the data relate to each other within the specific context of the space. By focusing on themes, it was possible to explore how the informal beginnings and subsequent formalizations of the art center influenced its current practices and interactions. Furthermore, it allowed for flexibility and reflexivity: unlike some other methods that impose predefined categories or frameworks, this approach is flexible and allows for an evolving understanding of the data. It encourages reflection on how perspectives and experiences influence the interpretation of issues. In this case, this meant considering how my participation in participant observation and interviews might shape my understanding of Associazione Bastione. The method supported the development of insights and theories based on the data. For this dissertation, reflexive thematic analysis allowed me to create a framework for understanding the role of the independent arts centre in the arts market and community, based on the themes that emerged from the data. It was also useful for increasing the depth of analysis by focusing on the meanings and implications of the themes identified. This depth is crucial for understanding how Associazione Bastione functions and interacts within its environment.

5.4 Limitations

This study is shaped by a number of limitations that deserve careful reflection. First, the notion of “independent art space” itself poses conceptual challenges. The literature reviewed highlights the diversity and evolving nature of these spaces, yet no unified definition exists. The term encompasses a broad spectrum of initiatives, from informal, artist-run collectives to more structured non-profit organizations, whose meanings and configurations vary across socio-cultural contexts. This definitional ambiguity could be considered a limitation, but it is also what renders these spaces analytically interesting. Rather than imposing a fixed typology, the thesis embraces this diversity, proposing a working definition that foregrounds autonomy, situated practice and collective governance as key features. This allows for a broad investigation that is attentive to the specificity and heterogeneity of the phenomenon under study.

The decision to center the empirical analysis on a single case study also has implications for the generalizability of the findings. A case study approach necessarily limits the scope of comparative inference. However, it simultaneously enables a depth of insight that would be difficult to achieve through broader, more superficial methods. While the findings may not be universally transferable, they offer conceptual tools and insights that can inform the analysis of similar spaces in other contexts. A further limitation is the size and composition of the sample. Ten artists affiliated with Associazione Bastione participated in semi-structured interviews, supported by participant observation over a six-month period. A broader sample, including external stakeholders or audiences, might have offered a wider range of perspectives, but the focused engagement with a small group enabled a more in-depth exploration of the organizational culture, artistic intentions, and everyday practices of those directly involved. This level of proximity facilitated a granular understanding of the values, negotiations, and tensions that shape the life of the space. The time-limited nature of the fieldwork is also acknowledged; six months provided substantial insight into the organization’s dynamics, but longer-term transformations and relationships with the wider ecosystem may extend beyond the temporal scope of this research.

The qualitative nature of the methodology offers rich and contextualized insights, but necessarily introduces a degree of subjectivity. The role of the researcher, as both observer and interpreter, is never neutral. To address this, the study embraces reflexivity as a methodological strength as it enhances the transparency and interpretive depth of the findings.

Finally, certain limitations emerge in relation to the use of the VBA as the central analytical framework. The VBA offers a robust lens for capturing the plurality of values embedded in cultural practices—across market, government, social, personal, and transcendental spheres—yet its application also raises conceptual and practical challenges. First, the spheres, while conceptually distinct, often collapse in practice: artists navigate overlapping and sometimes conflicting value logics. In this sense, the five-sphere model can struggle to fully account for the ambivalence, friction, and fluidity that characterize everyday artistic decision-making—particularly in spaces that are self-organized, precarious, and constantly evolving. Moreover, the VBA's emphasis on valorization as a shared, dialogical process can underplay structural inequalities and conditions of access. It allows us to see how artists and collectives generate value in non-instrumental and relational terms, but it is less well-equipped to analyze how such practices are constrained by broader systems (e.g. funding regimes, urban redevelopment).

Chapter 6

Context: Contextualizing alternative cultural production in Turin

To understand how independent art practices reshape cultural production, it is essential first to consider the broader urban, social, and political environment in which these practices occur. This chapter provides the contextual groundwork necessary for answering the third sub-research question: What contextual conditions (urban, social and political) enable or constrain alternative modes of cultural production? Through an examination of Turin's socio-political history, urban regeneration processes, cultural policy frameworks, and social dynamics, the chapter establishes the setting within which Associazione Bastione operates. In doing so, it sets the stage for the empirical findings and deeper analytical discussion presented in the subsequent chapters, highlighting why and how contextual factors play a pivotal role in enabling or constraining the development and sustainability of independent art spaces.

6.1 The contemporary art scene in Italy and Turin: Historical networks and current dynamics

Historically, professional networks have significantly shaped the development of contemporary art in Italy by facilitating connections among artists, institutions, and local communities, and influencing cultural production across multiple decades (Fiorentino et al., 2010). This section examines how these networks have evolved and how their current configurations affect alternative artistic practices, particularly in relation to the urban context of Turin—the setting for Associazione Bastione.

Understanding this evolution and the present-day role of networks provides crucial insights into the broader conditions that frame grassroots artistic initiatives and their relationship with local communities, institutions, and the market.

6.1.1 The contemporary art market in Italy: Networks, dynamics and structural constraints

Understanding the contemporary art ecosystem in Italy requires considering both the general international market model and distinct national dynamics. At its core, the Italian contemporary art market mirrors global structures, with artists driving innovation, galleries facilitating market entry and recognition, museums and institutions (such as MAXXI in Rome and Castello di Rivoli in Turin) providing platforms for exhibiting and preserving contemporary art, and critics and curators shaping artistic reputations (Zorloni, 2005; Brunelli, 2015). Private collectors and patrons support this ecosystem through acquisitions and direct funding, their collections often becoming central to major museum exhibitions (Zorloni, 2019). International events such as the Venice Biennale play a crucial role in positioning Italian artists on the global stage, providing opportunities for visibility and networking (Zorloni, 2005).

However, the Italian context presents several unique structural constraints that limit opportunities, especially for emerging artists. Unlike more structured international contexts, the Italian art market is marked by a fragmented, unpredictable, and highly relational environment. Entry barriers are particularly high due to the limited presence of stable local networks, uneven institutional support, and the reduced role of art academies in preparing artists for professional careers (Bertacchini & Borrione, 2021). Young artists face pressure to cultivate relational capital extensively, often at the expense of their own artistic practice (Sacco, 2005). Relationships between artists and galleries are complicated by credibility issues and inconsistent professional standards, further constraining career development and international visibility (Santagata, 1995; Trimarchi, 2004). Additionally, the Italian art market remains heavily dependent on public funds and

private foundations, such as bank foundations, highlighting vulnerabilities in financial sustainability (Bertacchini and Santagata, 2012).

Art academies, despite their growing number, offer limited practical support for artists seeking to professionalize and internationalize their careers (see Table 6.1). The relatively low graduation and internationalization rates indicate a gap in Italy's ability to systematically foster and sustain artistic talent on an international scale.

	Academic year	N° of students	Internationals
Enrolled in the course	2021/2022	28.649	5.356
Enrolled in I grade	2021/2022	9.549	n/a
Graduates	2021	6.939	1.503

Table 6.1. A picture of the number and the characteristics of the students who attend the academies of art in Italy. Source: author's elaboration based on data from the Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca, 2023.

Since April 2019, the Italian Council has broadened its horizons by extending its support to international initiatives involving Italian artists, curators and critics. The program now funds artists' residencies abroad, as well as projects dedicated to the creation of monographic exhibitions in foreign cultural institutions or editorial activities focused on Italian contemporary art. These projects must involve collaboration with international cultural institutions and include an international promotion component. At the local level, the Association for the Network of Young Italian Artists (GAI) supports artists under the age of 35 through educational and promotional initiatives. It runs a popular website with profiles of young creators and works with partner organizations.

Despite the presence of academies and international, national and local networks, recent reports show that the presence of Italian artists abroad is rather limited. According to the report on the visibility of Italian contemporary art abroad, the best-selling Italian artists from 1999 to 2021 are predominantly associated with the Arte Povera movement (Barrilà et al., 2022). The analysis focuses on Italian

contemporary artists born after 1960. Italian art revenues increased from \$1.1 million to \$3.7 million over the past 21 years, with notable peaks attributed to the artist Maurizio Cattelan. However, the average price for Italian artists fell by 81% and the market became more fragmented, with 509 artists in 2021 compared to 17 in 2000. Contemporary French artists, on the other hand, saw sales increase by 9,214% to \$26 million, with an average price of \$13,153. The number of French artists also increased significantly. German contemporary artists experienced significant growth, with sales increasing from \$107,992 to \$22.4 million and the number of artists increasing from 20 to 408. The average price rose to \$20,619. Overall, the Italian market struggled to keep up with its French and German counterparts in terms of growth and stability. In 2021, only two Italian artists born after 1960 made it into Artprice's top 100 Italian artists of the 20th century by turnover: Cattelan and Matteo Pugliese. However, their auction values are significantly lower than those of their contemporaries in France and Germany. German and French artists born after 1960 dominate the top 100 list in 2021, with much higher turnover than their Italian counterparts. This highlights a significant disparity in the auction market for contemporary Italian art.

Figure 6.1. Italian sales: Top ten Italian artists by total sales from 1999 to 2021 Data in millions of pounds. Source: Barrilà et al., 2022.

6.1.2 Turin's contemporary art scene from Arte Povera to the present day

Turin, a city historically overshadowed by Rome and Florence in the artistic arena, emerged in the late 20th century as a central center for contemporary art. The post-war period in Italy was characterized by a process of economic reconstruction, political instability and cultural renewal. The 1950s and 1960s were particularly significant as artists sought to break away from traditional forms and explore new media and concepts. During this period, avant-garde movements emerged, with Arte Povera being one of the most influential (Celant, 1969). ‘Arte povera’ (Poor art), was a radical art movement that emerged in the late 1960s. The term was coined by the art critic Germano Celant in 1967 (Celant, 1969). The movement was

characterized by the use of everyday materials such as earth, stones, paper and cloth to create art. It was a reaction against the commercialization of art and the prevailing consumer culture. The artists associated with Arte Povera sought to challenge the *status quo* and blur the boundaries between art and life. Key figures in Arte Povera included Michelangelo Pistoletto, Jannis Kounellis, Mario Merz and Alighiero Boetti. These artists created works that were both conceptually rigorous and aesthetically evocative, using a variety of materials and techniques. For instance, Pistoletto's use of mirrors in his works reflected his interest in the relationship between art and the viewer, while Merz's igloos made from various materials emphasized the intersection of nature and technology (Pistoletto, 1994).

Turin played a crucial role in the development and dissemination of Arte Povera. The city's industrial backdrop provided fertile ground for the movement's emphasis on ordinary materials and themes of transformation (Christov-Bakargiev, 1999). Turin's Fiat factories and industrial warehouses became symbols of modernity, influencing artists to incorporate elements of industrialization into their work. The Galleria Civica d'Arte Moderna e Contemporanea (GAM) and the Castello di Rivoli in Turin were instrumental in promoting and preserving Arte povera. These institutions not only housed important collections of Arte povera artworks, but also facilitated exhibitions that highlighted the legacy of the movement. For example, the Castello di Rivoli's extensive collection continues to attract international attention and serves as a testament to the continuing importance of the movement (Lumley, 2005). Today, Turin remains a vibrant center for contemporary art, building on the legacy of Arte povera. The city hosts numerous art fairs. Artissima, for example, attracts artists, collectors and critics from all over the world. This annual event underlines Turin's commitment to contemporary art and provides a platform for emerging and established artists (Artissima, 2024). Moreover, contemporary art in Turin is characterized by a combination of historical influences and innovation. Artists in Turin today continue to explore themes central to Arte povera, such as materiality, space and socio-political commentary, while also incorporating new media and formats (Artissima, 2024).

6.1.3 An overview of the history and dynamics of independent art spaces in Italy and of the role played by the city of Turin

The international revolutionary wave of 1968 created a climate of protest and demands for change in Europe, spanning the social, political, economic and cultural spheres. Artistically, the processual, minimalist and conceptual movements emerging in the United States, reflecting new relationships between art and society, were interpreted and adapted according to regional contexts. In Italy, the Arte povera movement aligned itself with the international avant-garde, seeking both artistic and social renewal. Between 1967 and 1971, Celant's leadership through exhibitions and critical texts positioned Arte Povera at the forefront of experimental art. His essay, 'Arte povera: appunti per una guerriglia' ('Notes for a guerrilla war'), published in *Flash Art* in 1967, articulated the movement's radical stance, claiming that Arte povera did not engage with established social or cultural systems, but sought to disrupt conventional expectations in a world dominated by the market systems (Celant, 1967).

Although linked to institutional galleries, Arte Povera also had links with alternative spaces such as 'Deposito d'Arte Presente', an independent gallery in Turin founded by Gian Enzo Sperone in 1967. Until its closure in 1969, this space became an important venue for exhibitions and performances, offering an alternative to the market-driven gallery system and filling institutional gaps in supporting new artistic experimentation (Balbi, 2020). During this period, Italy witnessed an increase in participation in social and political movements, which gained new momentum following the administrative decentralization of 1970. This reform transferred power from the state to regional governments, allowing for greater local involvement and fostering a sense of direct participation in community governance. Artists responded to these changes by forming militant, self-governing collectives that sought to bring art into urban spaces and align themselves with social and political movements. Collectives such as 'Lavoro Uno' (1972-73) and the 'Collettivo Autonomo di Porta Ticinese' (1974) in Milan, as well as 'Ambulanti' in Naples and the 'Laboratorio di Comunicazione Militante' in Milan (both founded in 1975), aimed to actively intervene in society and contribute to its

transformation (Pioselli, 2015). These independent spaces also represented alternative venues for artistic production, debate and collaboration. Often linked to international networks, they engaged with international art spaces. An early example is Zona, an independent art space founded in Florence in 1974 by a collective of artists, musicians, poets and architects. Entirely self-funded, Zona was conceived as an alternative to institutional systems that were seen as hierarchical and exclusionary, particularly towards contemporary art practices from outside the major cities (Dettere and Nannucci, 2012).

The rise of independent art spaces in Italy is marked by a few notable practices that have successfully cultivated participation, dialogue and artistic production outside traditional institutional frameworks. These spaces are deeply influenced by their socio-cultural contexts and the local communities they serve, reflecting the rich regional diversity that characterizes Italy. This territorial specificity has allowed the development of independent initiatives that are closely linked to local conditions, while at the same time seeking to be connected to broader national and international networks (Delfini, 2009).

6.2 Urban regeneration processes in Italy: The case of Turin

Urban regeneration has increasingly become central to urban policy agendas in Italy, driven by the need to address complex socio-economic and physical challenges facing contemporary cities. Historically, urban planning in Italy has been deeply connected to preserving and enhancing cultural heritage. However, in recent decades, this approach has broadened significantly, integrating contemporary cultural and artistic practices to foster social inclusion and economic revitalization (Bianchini and Parkinson, 1993). Within this broader context, artistic interventions and grassroots cultural activities have emerged as critical catalysts in transforming urban spaces, often initiating broader processes of community engagement and spatial revitalization.

The city of Turin offers a compelling example of how these dynamics unfold within an urban context shaped profoundly by industrial heritage. Once dominated by automobile manufacturing and heavy industry, Turin has experienced significant

structural transformation, leaving behind numerous abandoned industrial sites. These sites have become focal points for urban regeneration strategies, often involving cultural and creative projects aimed at redefining urban identities and promoting social cohesion.

The following sections explore in depth the specific ways in which Turin has harnessed artistic and cultural initiatives within its urban regeneration framework. This analysis will provide essential context for understanding the enabling and constraining factors that shape independent cultural production, particularly within grassroots artistic spaces such as Associazione Bastione. By examining Turin's regeneration strategies, including policy frameworks, institutional dynamics, and community responses, the analysis lays the groundwork for comprehensively addressing the research question related to the contextual conditions facilitating or hindering alternative modes of cultural production.

6.2.1 Urban regeneration through cultural and artistic practices in Italy

Urban regeneration in Italy has evolved from post-war reconstruction efforts to more integrated strategies that address both physical decline and socio-economic issues. Initially, urban regeneration was primarily concerned with repairing the damage caused by the Second World War and accommodating industrial growth (Saccomani, 2016). However, with the industrial decline and deindustrialization of the 1970s and 1980s, particularly in northern cities such as Milan and Turin, the focus of urban regeneration shifted. Indeed, the emphasis shifted from large-scale infrastructure projects to more sustainable, community-driven approaches that addressed social cohesion and economic diversification (Marra et al., 2016; Mariotti and Riganti, 2021).

Increasingly, the role of arts has gained growing prominence in contemporary discussions on urban regeneration, recognized as key drivers of social transformation. Their impact is explored in academic debates concerning cultural policy frameworks, which embrace concepts like the cultural district (Santagata, 2006). Cultural and artistic urban regeneration refers to the use of cultural and creative practices as a means of reimagining and revitalising urban spaces. Both

cultural and artistic interventions have become increasingly central to urban regeneration projects in Italy as they engage communities, foster social entrepreneurship, activate neglected spaces and contribute to the socio-economic revitalization of cities (Baraldi and Salone, 2022). Regeneration projects are often characterized by an emphasis on inclusivity, participation and experimentation, offering alternative forms of urban regeneration that resist top-down planning models (Amato and Bevilacqua, 2020). These projects often take place in spaces that have been marginalized by dominant cultural and economic systems, such as former industrial zones or underdeveloped urban areas, where they create new opportunities for cultural and economic activity. Cultural and artistic practices in urban regeneration can take various forms, from large-scale public art installations to social centers and community-based projects. In Italy, such initiatives have been driven by both institutional actors and grassroots organizations, with varying degrees of success (Borchi, 2018). They have been particularly important in regions with weaker institutional support for contemporary art and culture, where independent cultural actors have sought to fill the gap left by public policy (Faraci, 2017). The greater challenge has been the discourse between local governments and the bottom-up, and even where specific regulations and local agreements exist, the legal framework has proved insufficient to manage these practices in the most effective way (Lenna et al., 2020).

6.2.2 From industrial to creative city: urban regeneration and informal practices in Turin and the case of Cavallerizza Reale

Once one of Italy's industrial centers, Turin has undergone a significant transformation in recent decades. Faced with economic decline in the second half of the 20th century due to the collapse of its industrial base, the city turned to culture, creativity and innovation as key components of its regeneration strategy (Vanolo, 2015). Throughout the 20th century, Turin's development was closely linked to its industrial sector, particularly the automobile industry. As the headquarters of Fiat and a center of heavy industry, Turin became synonymous with industrial productivity and working-class identity. In the 1970s and 1980s,

however, deindustrialization began to take hold, leading to widespread unemployment, urban decay and social unrest (Scamuzzi, 2022). The decline of manufacturing has left much of the city's industrial landscape derelict, presenting both challenges and opportunities for future development. The economic downturn of the 1980s and 1990s forced Turin to rethink its urban development strategies. The post-industrial crisis necessitated a shift from reliance on traditional industries to a more diversified economy that included culture, technology and services (Vanolo, 2015). This period marked the beginning of Turin's transition from an industrial city to a creative city, driven by urban regeneration policies that sought to repurpose abandoned spaces and attract new forms of cultural and economic activity. The 2006 Winter Olympics in Turin further accelerated the city's regeneration efforts, with significant public and private investment in infrastructure, tourism and cultural projects (Della Sala, 2023). These initiatives aimed to raise the city's global profile, while fostering local economic growth by supporting the creative industries.

While much of Turin's regeneration has been driven by formal policies and large-scale projects, informal practices have also played a crucial role in transforming the city's urban landscape, including a general shift towards people rather than just places (Marra et al, 2016). Informal urban regeneration refers to bottom-up initiatives led by local communities, artists and grassroots organizations, often operating outside formal institutional frameworks and led by young people (Ferrero Camoletto and Genova, 2019; Bertacchini et al., 2022). In some cases, these practices have emerged as a response to the gaps left by formal urban policies, particularly in peripheral or neglected areas of the city that have not benefited from official regeneration programs (Lenna et al., 2020). Accordingly, Turin is one of the cities where the legal framework has sometimes proved insufficient to give space to informal movements, as the experience of Asilo Occupato shows (Lenna et al., 2020). Despite the existence of the so-called 'Patti di collaborazione per i beni comuni' (Collaboration pacts for common goods), the social center was evicted in 2019, just as the 'Patti' came to life, proving that the application of the agreement in the city is still scarce. Fortunately, similar local agreements had worked in other

Italian cities, as the Asilo Filangieri in Naples and the Bologna experience show (Borchi, 2018; Zinzani and Proto, 2020).

The year 2019 saw a major eviction at Cavallerizza Reale, an 18th century royal building and UNESCO World Heritage Site in the center of Turin. A group of artists, activists and local citizens had occupied the building in 2014. The case of Cavallerizza Reale is interesting because of the historical, architectural and social relevance of the building, and especially because the process of reappropriation redefines the actors, objects and actions within it (Vassallo, 2014). Designed by the architect Benedetto Alfieri at the request of Charles Emmanuel II of Savoy to provide Turin with a military academy, the building was used until the end of the 19th century as a service area for the Royal Palace and the Savoy State Headquarters. In the mid-1950s, the State Police moved to a building on an adjacent street and the Cavallerizza was used as a vehicle depot, while part of the surrounding buildings were used as social housing. The surrounding buildings were used as social housing for postal workers.

At the end of the last century, the Municipality of Turin decided to buy the whole area with the idea of restoring it in the glorious wake of the Olympic Games, and to rebuild the unified project that links it to the Teatro Regio, the Palazzo Reale and the Cathedral. From 2001 to 2013 it was temporarily entrusted to the Teatro Regio di Torino. In the same years, art exhibitions and events were held in some of the rooms at Cavallerizza, such as the 'Biennale Internazionale Arte Giovane'. In 2011, the public administration decided to sell the building. After several attempts at public auction, it remained unsold until 2021, when it was bought by the Compagnia di San Paolo, a local banking and cultural foundation, and the University of Turin.

The occupation of the building took place between 2014 and 2019. On 23 May 2014, Cavallerizza was occupied by a group of workers in the field of arts and culture who decided to express their opposition to the sale of the building and to demand its cultural and public use. The assembly immediately called for a confrontation with the administration through formal communications and the use of the media, claiming legitimacy for the use of the space on the grounds of an

alternative and self-organized cultural offer. Students, citizens and some of Turin's cultural elite took part in the assembly. The occupation continued until 21 October 2019, when one of the buildings of the Cavallerizza was set on fire. The fire started in the former stables of the building, called 'Le Pagliere', where there are warehouses and material is stacked. The origin of the fire has never been clear: some have speculated that it was arson, but there is still no official confirmation. The fire marks a further weakening of a site that was already struggling due to difficult relations with the administration and surrounding museums. Thus, in November 2019, the police put an end to the occupation. Following these events, after the end of the occupation in November 2019, the building was sold in October 2021 to the only bidders, a banking foundation, Compagnia di San Paolo, an important financier of public and private bodies, and the University of Turin. The aim of the project is to provide a new venue for the cultural elite of the city. Moreover, they have supported proposals for the creation of high quality hospitality facilities.

During the years of occupation, and still today, Cavallerizza quickly became a symbol of resistance to neoliberal urban policies that priorities profit over the public interest. The occupation aimed to challenge the dominant narratives of urban regeneration, which often involve the gentrification of historic sites and the displacement of local communities (Cavallerizza Irreale, 2024). Instead, the occupiers proposed an alternative model of urban regeneration that prioritizes social inclusion, cultural production and public participation. The collective emphasized that Cavallerizza should remain a space for creativity, cultural exchange and grassroots organizing, rather than being subject to market forces. This experience calls for a right to the city, according to which citizens should produce urban spaces based on their needs. In this view, empty spaces become an opportunity and urban care a collective and shared task (Mattei and Quarta, 2015).

6.3 The practice of 'Associazione Bastione' in Turin: Context and case study

Following the previous sections on the dynamics of the contemporary art market and the cultural and creative ferment that characterizes urban regeneration in Turin,

it seems essential to broaden the understanding of the institutional context in order to better frame the practice of Associazione Bastione.

Beyond the micro level at which organisations such as Associazione Bastione operate, the macro and *meso* levels play a crucial role in shaping the ecosystem in which these practices take place. The aim of this section is to explore these levels in more detail, drawing an ecosystem of actors and highlighting how they interact with informal and more established artistic practices, which are involved both in the art market and in processes of urban regeneration. This approach will help to contextualize the empirical analysis of Associazione Bastione, which is deeply embedded in the context of Turin's cultural scene.

At the macro level, government policies - involving local, regional and central authorities - have a significant impact on the development of cultural and creative projects. Turin, like other Italian cities, has benefited from decentralization reforms, particularly since the 1970s, which have transferred a significant amount of decision-making power from central government to local authorities. In particular, since 1997, as part of the reform of the public administration and the simplification of administrative activities, a policy of decentralization has been initiated by Law no. 59/1997 (or 'Bassanini Law'), which includes the delegation to the Government of administrative functions and tasks to the Regions and local authorities, and the subsequent implementing decree (d. Legislative Decree no. 112/1998) of the aforementioned delegation, which carried out the conferral of functions and tasks to the local authorities in a number of matters expressly indicated, grouped in four sectors: economic development and productive activities; territory, environment and infrastructure; personal and community services; regional and local administrative police and the authorization system. This process of decentralization has enabled the city to develop policies that support local cultural production and urban regeneration initiatives. Municipal policies have prioritized the preservation of heritage sites while encouraging new forms of cultural and artistic experimentation that contribute to the economic and social regeneration of the city. Regional actors, such as the Regione Piemonte, reinforce this support through grants and programs specifically targeted at the cultural sector (Perulli, 2010).

At the *meso* level, a variety of actors are actively contributing to the cultural and urban regeneration processes in Turin. These include cultural institutions, non-profit organizations and accelerators for social and cultural innovation. Foundations such as Fondazione CRT and Compagnia di San Paolo have been key players in funding and promoting cultural projects, trying to act as intermediaries between local government and grassroots practices. Turin has also accelerators and incubators for social and cultural change, such as SocialFare and Torino Social Impact, which provide financial resources, mentoring and networking opportunities for emerging projects. These accelerators are conceived to play an essential role in fostering innovation and sustainability within grassroots organizations (Falomi and De Giorgio, 2019).

At the micro level, Turin has a thriving ecosystem of independent grassroots initiatives, with many peer organizations engaged in cultural and social regeneration (Bertacchini and Pazzola, 2015; Bertacchini et al., 2022). These organizations often share similar values and goals, focusing on reclaiming urban spaces for artistic production, community engagement and social activism. In many cases, they collaborate on projects or share resources to strengthen the cultural fabric of the city (Salone et al., 2017). For example, initiatives such as Cavallerizza Reale have set precedents for how informal practices can contribute to urban regeneration, often filling the gaps left by formal urban policies.

Figure 6.2 provides a map of Turin's cultural ecosystem and identifies Associazione Bastione on the map⁴.

⁴ The construction of the ecosystem was approached with methodological rigor, drawing on multiple data sources to ensure comprehensive coverage. Key resources included the map on contemporary art places and spaces during the local fair Artissima (Il Giornale dell'Arte – La Torino Art Map, 2023), which, while providing information on galleries and non-profit spaces within the contemporary art market (primary market), was not included in the final analysis due to its temporary nature. In addition, the local accelerator database (Torino Social Impact - Promotori e Partners, 2024), as well as the local associations and clubs database (Arci Torino – Circoli e Associazioni, 2024) were used to map social and cultural spaces. Furthermore, the ecosystem analysis was informed by previous research (Bertacchini et al., 2022), which provided data on visual art, cultural and social spaces (some spaces are not included because they are officially closed).

Figure 6.2. Map of Turin's cultural ecosystem. Source: author's own elaboration based on secondary data.

Although the artists of Bastione have a relationship with the structures of the market, as they are all visual artists trained at the Accademia Albertina (the city Academy), it should be noted that their origins are deeply rooted in the experience of grassroots, informal regeneration. In fact, their practice has its origins in Cavallerizza Reale, initially working within the walls of the bastion, one of the buildings of Cavallerizza, aligning themselves with the wider Cavallerizza Occupata movement. This movement, which emerged in response to the perceived underutilization of public spaces, sought to reclaim these spaces for cultural and artistic production, challenging conventional norms of public space use and ownership in urban contexts (Dellarossa, 2020). However, while Associazione Bastione shares a common origin with Cavallerizza Reale, the legal framework governing its current settlement at Villa Rey represents a notable shift towards a

more formal organization (namely an association: a non-profit). There, Associazione Bastione established its home and experimental space. Villa Rey, another historic building owned by the city of Turin, is now rented by the artists under a temporary administrative concession, a legal agreement that allows the association to use the property while maintaining public ownership. Although still temporary, this concession provides a degree of institutional recognition and stability that was lacking during the previous, informal occupation of the bastion at Cavallerizza. The administrative concession provides a legal framework within which the association can operate, but the temporary status also reflects the ongoing uncertainties that many grassroots artistic practices face in their interactions with municipal authorities and urban governance structures in this context⁵.

⁵ In administrative law, it is the act by which the public administration authorizes the concessionaire to utilize resources and/or conduct activities that are exclusively reserved for public authorities and are not accessible to private parties. The concession of public good, public service, and public work are the primary types that we differentiate. (Bara, 2018). The public good concession is applicable in this specific instance. The concession is typically granted for specific purposes, such as cultural or social activities, and is subject to conditions that the concessionaire must satisfy in order to preserve its rights. In practice, this concession enables municipalities to collaborate with cultural and non-profit organizations by providing them with access to historically significant buildings or other public spaces, frequently as part of broader urban regeneration strategies. Nevertheless, these agreements are temporary and are subject to periodic renewal, which creates an environment of uncertainty for the occupying organizations (Novara, 2015).

Chapter 7

Findings: Artistic and organizational practices of ‘Associazione Bastione’

This chapter addresses the central research question and related sub-questions through an empirical analysis guided by an abductive approach. The main research question explored is:

How do independent art spaces reshape the boundaries between the market, the public sector, and the civil sphere in contemporary cultural production?

This is further articulated through the following sub-questions:

1. In what ways do independent art spaces organize cultural production through collective use, co-creation, and situated governance?
2. How do these practices generate and negotiate value(s) that escape conventional economic or policy-driven evaluative frameworks?
3. What contextual conditions (urban, social, political) enable or constrain these alternative modes of cultural production?

The findings presented in this chapter emerged from a thematic analysis that combined deductive conceptual frameworks, notably the Value-Based Approach (VBA), with inductive insights gathered from field data. Interviews and participant observations were conducted, focusing on Associazione Bastione's artistic and organizational practices. The analysis evolved iteratively, with insights from the empirical data refining and extending initial theoretical expectations. A narrative approach is employed to guide the reader through the empirical insights, mirroring the research process that unfolded through dialogues, observational events, and

documentary materials collected at Bastione. This narrative captures the historical trajectory of the group, from its initial informal activities in the occupied Cavallerizza Reale to its structured existence at Villa Rey. The resulting thematic analysis explores how Associazione Bastione experience artistic creation, collective governance, community care, financial sustainability and artistic autonomy. In doing so, this chapter also highlights aspects common to similar independent art spaces identified in existing literature, e.g. their emphasis on collective governance and community engagement, while delineating the specific contextual factors and practices that distinguish Associazione Bastione within the broader landscape of independent art spaces. To help the reader follow the presentation of findings, Figure 7.1 shows Bastione's timeline.

Figure 7.1 The artists of Bastione and their timeline. Source: author's own elaboration based on Bastione archives.

The core team at Associazione Bastione comprises ten artists with a variety of technical skills, blending visual arts, music, performance and creative writing. This variety of interests enables each artist to conduct their own research across various disciplines. External collaborations also reflect the collective's wide-ranging interests, creating a path that embraces multiple artistic languages. Since its inception, the group has been involved with Bastione San Maurizio, contributing their skills to build an ecosystem and define each member's role. In addition to the current members, it is important to acknowledge the founders of the collective in 2017: Lisa Redetti, Cecilia Ceccherini, Mara Jvonne Raja, Gianmaria Della Rossa and Adele Zunino.

7.1 Redefining the way artists make art, network and build careers

7.1.1 The first experience at Bastione San Maurizio, Cavallerizza Reale: The space as installation

The group of artists now known as ‘Associazione Bastione’ was born in Turin in 2017, when 15 young artists began the occupation of the Bastione San Maurizio, one of the buildings of Cavallerizza Reale.

Figure 7.2 "Act I" 2017 Bastione Collective Exhibition: First Public Opening. Source: Bastione archives.

Their aim was to work together to activate the potential of the space through collaborative artistic practices, through an architectural and creative restoration. After about a month of experimenting within the site, the group formalized their efforts in a project called ‘Apotema’ (2017) - their first public exhibition at the bastion (Dellarosa, 2020). The name, derived from geometry, refers to the radius of an inscribed circle and symbolizes the relationships and movements within the space, the way the artists liked to visually describe their ongoing activities in the space at the time. This project marked the official start of the architectural and creative interventions in the building, and the bastion became a house of sculptures,

where the architectural features and individual works merged into an evolving installation. Each artist left a trace, creating a layered history of interventions within the space. For example, Emanuele Marullo's 'Nord-Est' featured a bamboo dome originally intended for the adjacent gardens but assembled indoors.

Figure 7.3 Nord-Est': Emanuele Marullo's bamboo dome conceived for the Cavallerizza gardens, assembled inside the Bastion. Source: Bastione archives.

He used seasonal elements from the garden within the structure, merging the exterior and interior environments. Giulia Rebonato's 'Ospite' repurposed bricks from an unsealed balcony door to reimagine a once-blocked passageway, giving it a new identity. Donato Mariano's 'Untitled' confronted the invasive construction history of the bastion by painting directly on the existing brick layers to reveal their historical significance. Mohsen Baghernejad's 'The Way of Why' was an enigmatic phrase into a wall and had it later plastered over, leaving the message almost invisible but symbolically present. Other contributions included Lisa Redetti's sound installation 'Zoom 01', which captured ambient sounds and fragments of past

life within the bastion, reactivated through audio-visual interaction, and Marco Mattana's 'In Divenire', a contemporary fresco that stood in stark contrast to the previous vandalism by re-imagining the space for a more intimate engagement with the audience.

By the end of the first year (2017), the expected restoration of the Bastione San Maurizio by the local government had not begun, giving the artists the freedom to expand their presence and activities. This led to the launch of 'AFFITTASI'⁶ in January 2019, a project that invited external artists and groups to engage with the bastion and its artists, transforming the location into an artistic hub. The initiative facilitated performances and installations from a wider artistic community, extending the reach of the group's influence. In general, multidisciplinary was the *fil rouge* that linked these and other events: between 2017 and 2019, similar artistic projects have been hosted and co-organized, such as 'K_Night' by the 'Mrzb' collective and 'DISCARNATE: the flesh failures' by the American artist Qualiatik, as well as documentaries and sound performances such as 'Gang of ducks x Cripta 747'. According to the artists, "music, performance and visual art have allowed different personalities, both hosted and belonging to the main group of artists, to express themselves during this period".

However, this period of experimentation came to an end on 19 November 2019 with the start of the eviction process led by local authorities. This marked a significant turning point for the artists in the group, but also for all the artists and people who used the spaces in Cavallerizza as an artistic hub⁷. From that moment on, the artists of the bastion began to reflect on important questions about their role in caring for abandoned urban spaces and their relationship with the creation of communities.

⁶ The Italian word means 'to rent'. In fact, it was a project based on the contradictory idea of renting space in the occupied building for free.

⁷ For an overview of the occupation at Cavallerizza, see chapter 6

Figure 7.4 Bastione San Maurizio, Upper Gardens of the Cavallerizza Reale. Source: Bastione archives.

7.1.2 Space for creation

The first years of the group of artists, spent at the Bastione San Maurizio (Figure 7.4) on the Upper Gardens of the Cavallerizza Reale, tell us about the dynamics, the understanding, the initial organization of an independent art space where artists act independently of the market. The dominant understanding of independent art spaces in economic and humanistic studies focuses on their detachment from the traditional art market. Literature identifies these spaces as environments free from commercial pressures in which artistic experimentation and dissemination flourish. Art spaces are described as initiatives that operate outside the boundaries of the market, characterized by their own organization, rules, ideologies (Sharon, 1979; Blessi at al., 2011). However, the experience of the group at the bastion in its first informal years indeed proves that independence is a strategic rather than ideological choice, made primarily to support artistic creation that involves experimentation outside the constraints of the market. Especially in these first years (2017-2019), their professional life was all about experimentation: they did not really have any

contacts with galleries or curators: "Sometimes we invited the artists who taught at the Academy. But very few of them came to see our practice and our work at the bastion". This shows a kind of rejection, or simply disinterest, in their informal practice on the part of institutional education, but it is also consistent with their initial detachment from the Academy and more institutional environments: "The academy itself did not have spaces for us to meet, create and think. So we had to find our own space"; "it wasn't so much a decision to refuse the system ideologically, but rather to find a place where we could work and experiment without having to wait for someone to give us a chance". Another artist argues: "The Bastione San Maurizio was like a blank canvas where we could make things happen without waiting for permission". Therefore, with the occupation of the Bastione San Maurizio in 2017, the group found a way to get around the constraints imposed by the academic institution. At the bastion, they were able to express and sometimes develop their creative ideas, interacting directly with other artists, not only in the visual arts but also in music and theatre. Fostering a sense of artistic community has been crucial to their artistic development and has influenced their practice, which has become multidisciplinary.

This phase of creating with the space, connecting with other artists through multidisciplinary was never described as 'independent' by the artists during the interviews and observations, although much of the literature tends to focus on their conscious break with the market, especially in regards to historic independent art centers in the 90s (Sharon, 1979; Blessi et al., 2011; Arthurs, 2012; Dettere and Nannucci, 2012; Haghighat, 2020). Their relationship with the market is often much more complex. For some, engagement with the bastion was a matter of creative freedom, while for others it was a practical choice dictated by the availability of resources (space and technology) and relationships. According to their description of the years at the Bastion, they were trying to make art both as individuals (their thesis work) and through collective projects (to experiment with others). The thesis work was more of a temporary phase; it was primarily about continuing their individual artistic research with great freedom to experiment. This also provided the opportunity for some to complete a genuine return on their research, culminating

in a final thesis project. The space and time that was missing in the academy were provided here—this proximity between the Cavallerizza and the Academy allowed for a unique environment where both personal and collective artistic explorations could thrive.

As such, the label 'independent' does not adequately capture the realities of these artists' early careers, nor does it reflect the variety of roles they played within the broader ecosystem of Cavallerizza. In general, the definition of independence fails to recognize the inherent flexibility and diversity within these spaces, particularly in the early stages when they are free from institutional constraints (Arthurs, 2012). The bastion experience acted as a community hub for artistic creation. One artist explained that the idea of their space was “to continue our personal paths... while involving other figures in the arts, such as theatre and music”. These spaces may not reject the market altogether, but create parallel structures that allow for more creative autonomy. Independent artists are better understood through a more sophisticated lens that takes into account their practical, social and contextual motivations. Artists working in independent spaces do not always reject the market outright, but make strategic decisions about when and how to engage with it. Similarly, the diverse formats and agendas of independent spaces reflect a range of responses to the challenges facing contemporary artists, from the need for creative autonomy to the desire for support from other artists. The concept of an independent artist or space should therefore not be seen as a static or absolute quality, but as a flexible strategy that artists and collectives adopt in response to their particular circumstances.

7.1.3 Network and careers

The previous section explains how the creation of the informal group at the bastion was not that ideological, but rather a practical need for creative experimentation in a shared space. Although the artists did not openly refuse the art market, they did recognize the importance of creating their art in a shared space as a way of overcoming the problem of high barriers to entry into the art market

(Zorloni and Ardizzone, 2016). According to one of the artists, "there were no opportunities to work together at the academy or in the galleries. We needed a space where we could just try things out together, without formalities". And also, "it wasn't so much a decision to reject the system ideologically, but rather to find a place where we could work and experiment without having to wait for someone to give us a chance". The development of the group at the Bastione San Maurizio is another example of how the creation of such spaces is a response to specific practical needs to create their own ecosystem. This section explores two main reasons why these spaces have emerged as practical solutions: the need for informal networking, and the desire to build careers independent of the conventional art market through their own network and relationships.

For young artists, the early stages of their careers are characterized by a strong need to experiment, collaborate and connect with fellow artists and, at the same time, high barriers set by gatekeepers (Quemin, 2013). In fact, the rigid structures of the traditional art market and its associated institutions often limit opportunities for young emerging artists (Sacco, 2005). Galleries, museums and established networks are often inaccessible to those without the right connections or sufficient market recognition (Thompson, 2008). As one artist argued, "We felt cut off from the mainstream galleries because we were young and had no network. It felt like a closed club". As a result, artists face significant barriers when trying to enter the art world through these traditional channels. The early members of the group, many of whom were recent art school graduates, were frustrated by the lack of accessible, shared spaces for co-creation and artistic dialogue. The practice of occupying space and working closely with fellow artists was not only about artistic creation, but also about addressing the fundamental need for a supportive and engaged artistic community - something that traditional art institutions often fail to provide: "We built a network at the bastion that allowed us to work together in a way that the academy or the galleries never could."

The second major factor behind the creation of the space at the bastion was the desire to build careers that did not depend on the market conventional careers, which always lead artists to the mechanism of building visibility (Sacco, 2005). In

their plans, the creation of a space for creation and relationships could allow them to pursue parallel careers - one that could potentially interact with the market and another that existed outside. For those who already wanted to engage with the market and exhibit in galleries as a parallel career to the independent art space, the space offered a way to maintain a sense of autonomy and creative freedom. They could continue to experiment and develop their artistic voices independently, without being beholden to the demands of the market. "The bastion gave us a space to continue working on projects that the galleries might not be interested in, but that were important to us as artists," explained one of them. For others, the decision to bypass the market altogether was already a conscious one. These artists refuse the commodification of their work and the constraints imposed by galleries, collectors and museums. Instead, they focus on building autonomous careers, supported by alternative forms of support such as collaborations, residencies and teaching. As one artist described: "For me, it's not about selling art. It's about creating something meaningful and connecting with people through that process". For them, the existence of spaces such as the bastion was crucial, providing an environment in which they could work without the pressure of market expectations.

However, there is more to it than that. As they experienced the creation of artworks and the organization of exhibitions and performances with hosted artists, they began to realize that their way of working was no longer limited to the creation of art. They could build their artistic practice and careers around the organization of such art projects, which relied much more on hospitality and co-creation than on individual creation or creation as a collective of artists. Over the next few years (especially at Villa Rey), this possibility of a new career in their practice became visible to most of them, while others continued to focus on making art between their safe space and the market. In this sense, their words and practices may reflect a wider shift in which artists are taking control of their careers and artistic practices. Rather than waiting for market validation, they are creating their own platforms where they define their careers. This autonomy could allow for greater flexibility and freedom, enabling artists to pursue projects that may not be commercially viable but remain artistically significant. As one artist said: "The collaborations we

have built at the bastion are some of the most important relationships of my career. They're not about money, they're about shared ideas and support.

7.1.4 The development of new formats

The current contemporary art ecosystem is built on market dynamics: mechanisms that have grown over the years, based on the generation of value from the exchange of immaterial (information) and material (artworks) assets. Artists' lives, practices and careers are built precisely on these exchanges, values and shared (or not) information, with the problem that information is in surplus and unevenly distributed (Trimarchi, 2011; Roder and Thompson, 2013; Zorloni, 2013; Quemin, 2013). In other words, their position in the market is defined by the fairs, galleries or museums at which they exhibit (Zorloni, 2005; Thornton, 2012). Galleries strongly influence artists' success, which depends on their role within the market, the reach of their network (Benhamou et al., 2002), and the exhibition strategies they adopt, such as deliberately limiting the number of artworks shown in an exhibition (Velthuis, 2003). At the bastion, none of these rules applied, since cross-fertilization and multidisciplinary were at the heart of the artists who occupied Cavallerizza. All the artists at Cavallerizza (visual arts, music, theatre) collaborated among themselves and across disciplines, fostering an environment where creative ideas and practices intersected. This mix of skills and perspectives allowed them to experiment with new forms of production beyond artistic creation. As one artist said: "We didn't just exhibit, we created, built and collaborated on everything from logistics to the artworks themselves". This multi-dimensional way of working was essential to the way the group worked, encouraging the co-creation of work and blurring traditional boundaries between roles and disciplines.

Through collaborative practices, artists at the bastion began to explore new formats of making and exhibiting, reappropriating their space and building local communities. The space itself, deeply embedded in the urban context of Turin, served not only as a site for artistic production, but also as a hub for community creation. By involving the community (made up of artists, students, residents, professors) in their events, they cultivated a sense of collective ownership of the

space, transforming it into a platform for artistic experimentation, co-creation and civic participation (Figure 7.5). As one artist explained, their events were "designed to bring people together and foster connections within and beyond the art world". As another artist noted, "In galleries and museums, everything feels predetermined, even the roles. At bastion we created our own space to experiment without those constraints". Through a practice of collaboration and co-creation, they created a model of cross-fertilization and multi-disciplinarity that began to shape their artistic practice as a collective of artists. This is where the boundaries between heritage conservation, visual arts, performance, musical experimentation and social practice truly blur. And these are the premises of their current practice at Villa Rey.

Figure 7.5 NFF 2023 - A festival dedicated to the underground sounds of the contemporary electronic scene. Collaboration between RBL Torino and Bastione. Closing day of the festival featuring a bamboo architecture installation created during a workshop organized by the association and led by Emanuele Marullo, designed for the performance space and sound diffusion. Source: LLumCollettivo

7.2 Caring for the space as a home where communities are built through hospitality and co-creation

7.2.1 From the eviction to the Villa: Bastione as a temporary collective and the first period in Villa Rey

The practice within the walls of the Bastione San Maurizio in Cavallerizza Reale was fundamental to the way the group of artists built their practice and organization in the years that followed. The pillars were the reappropriation of the space and the co-creation and cross-fertilization with other artists and disciplines. Indeed, what really built their current practice in all its forms was the presence of a space where the artists could create, experiment and cross-fertilize. This intense relationship with the space as a group became even more evident when they lost the space of the bastion, after being evicted from Cavallerizza in November 2019. Indeed, the building had created a strong sense of identity for the group, and even after the eviction, the desire to continue the project remained alive. Without a space, the group adapted to the changes by becoming nomadic, where the people rather than the space became the constituent elements of the practice. And only then did they define themselves as a collective of artists. This adaptability was the basis for the evolution of the project and the promotion of new relationships and new balances within the collective. Already in 2019, the collective participated in an artistic residency promoted by MOMUC (The Ceramic Museum of Mondovì) in a small town of the Piedmont region, where they actively engaged with the city and the urban community through their artistic practice. The artists, who were working with ceramics for the first time, were invited to reshape the urban context of the city, whether inhabited or abandoned, through small interventions that would allow citizens to rediscover the places of their everyday lives and thus to participate in remembering or discovering. In this museum residency, the involvement of local citizens was crucial, with actions such as the distribution of coffee cups decorated by the artists in bars and restaurants to promote the final exhibition of the residency: 'Land Land Land'. They also explored abandoned spaces in the area, incorporating

found objects into their work and raising awareness of the potential of reclaiming abandoned urban spaces.

During this nomadic period the foundations were laid for the collective's next practice at Villa Rey. The year 2020 marked the end of the nomadic period, when the artists arrived at their new location, Villa Rey, a seventeenth-century villa on the hills of Turin. The villa was originally built as a family residence by the Turinetti di Priero family in the late 1600s. Later, financial hardships forced the Turinetti di Priero family to sell the villa, which changed ownership several times over the years. In 1780, the Marquis Carron di San Tommaso began to enlarge and restore the villa, but the work was never completed. Later, the Massimino di Ceva family carried out some work in the garden, and in 1872 the villa became the property of the Cavalier Giacomo Rey, who transformed it into a summer residence. After the death of Giacomo Rey's wife, Lidia, Villa Rey was inherited by their second son, Guido Rey. Guido's deep love of the mountains led him to move permanently to Valle d'Aosta, separating the family from Villa Rey. In 1933, the villa and the surrounding gardens were acquired by the City of Turin, which used the property for outdoor educational and recreational activities. During the Second World War, the villa was occupied by German troops, who used it as a refuge. In 2019, a 500-square-metre bunker, about 20 meters deep, was discovered on the site, probably built and used by the Nazis during the war. In 1946 Villa Rey was given to the ANPI (National Association of Italian Partisans) and in 1955 to the Associazione Campeggiatori Turistici d'Italia (Italian Tourist Camping Association), which used the garden as a camping site until 2014. Villa Rey has also been home to the Automotoclub Storico Italiano since 2006 and to the General Secretariat of the Fédération Internationale des Véhicules Anciens since 2018.

Meanwhile, in 1998 a private group of art conservators interested in the restoration and reuse of the building formed the Villa dell'Arte Association. In 2000, the Association was granted a concession for the restoration and reuse of Villa Rey. An educational restoration site was set up, with workshops led by students from the Accademia Albertina, coordinated by the restorer Antonio Rava, in collaboration

with the Piedmont Superintendencies and the Biotechnological Foundation⁸. The restoration project, financed by the Compagnia di San Paolo and the CRT Foundation, included major works such as the re-roofing and the restoration of decorative elements, frescoes, stuccoes and other features. Important parts of the villa have been restored, including the 17th and 18th century brick façades, the late 18th century atrium, the frescoed room on the ground floor depicting mythological themes and the paper-painted walls.

Figure 7.6 Villa Rey. Source: Bastione archives

⁸ The Municipal Council's decision of 11 April 2000 (200002829/08) authorised the concession of the building to the Villa dell'Arte Association (ONLUS) to promote a project aimed at the artistic restoration and reuse of the building, as well as its reuse as a temporary centre for educational research and experimentation (Comune di Torino – Delibere, 2000).

After the restoration, a small part of the villa's concession remained with Villa dell'Arte, to which Associazione Bastione affiliated in 2021, taking the step from restoring the spaces to promoting and enhancing emerging art.

At their first home in Bastione San Maurizio at Cavallerizza Reale, the architecture of the bastion had provided an ideal setting for artistic experimentation within its decaying 18th century architecture and garden. As the group grew as a nomadic collective and during their first months at Villa Rey, their sense of commitment and care for the space did not disappear, but rather became more conscious and mature. They began to cultivate the garden and take care of the villa, with the aim of making it a place for hosting artists and organizing exhibition projects, just as in the bastion. These objectives allowed the collective to strengthen the bonds between them, keeping alive the desire to exist despite the loss of the original physical space at Cavallerizza. This feeling was further strengthened during the closure of Covid-19, when they spent several months in the villa in a "forced residency". This residency became a creative and organizational framework among the members, culminating in their first event in the new space: "Se non tocchi, non cade" (2021), "a celebration of disruption and renewal that not only involved the city's artistic community but also sought to involve the neighborhood".

Figure 7.7 'Se non tocchi, non cade'. Audience action during the destruction of one of the piñatas displayed in the gardens of Villa Rey. Source: Bastione archives; Photo: Chiara Inglese.

The event took the form of a performance involving all ten artists and aimed to reflect on the curatorial concept as a process of caring for and taking a stance within the space. It took place across all the spaces inhabited by the collective during their residency both inside the villa and outdoors. Every space within Villa Rey gained significance in this context and emphasized the importance of both the interior and exterior environments in shaping the artistic experience. This performance served as an inaugural event for their installation and activities at Villa Rey, aimed at educating the community about the need to engage with the open-air surrounding environment after months of lockdown. During the residency, each member had the freedom to intervene in the work of the others, with the potential to develop or even destroy it. This exploration of freedom fostered both collaboration and conflict, leading to a reassessment of individuality and collectivity.

"Se non tocchi, non cade" is the first event organized by Bastione at Villa Rey, a project developed during the pre- and post-pandemic period, a time when the group found itself without a physical meeting space and uncertain about its future activities. Thanks to the collaboration with Associazione Villa dell'Arte, Bastione had the opportunity to activate a space immersed in the greenery of the hills of Turin. The project is a journey of shared experience, revolving around the themes of trust, coexistence, tolerance, and diversity. It takes shape precisely when sharing and proximity are discouraged or even denied during the isolation period. The experiment was to propose actions and gestures that could serve as the foundation for further interventions: each artist in the group was free to intervene on the work of others, with the possibility of further developing it or even destroying it. This process of defining freedoms generated a dimension of collaboration but also conflict, questioning the concepts of individuality and collectivity. The culmination occurred through an event in which the public was invited to participate, in a festive atmosphere, in the destruction of piñata sculptures created by the Bastione artists.

This was followed by a series of events using a wide variety of media and formats. 'Deserto' (Desert) was a theatrical performance resulting from the collaboration with the Scuola di Teatro Sergio Tofano. A dialogue between the actors and the set design conceived by Bastione. In the same days, Bastione hosted a series of reflections on clubbing and the space following the pandemic and lockdown in the form of an event called 'Culto' (Cult). In November, the project 'Amore mio' (My love) was organized to host a music and art project by an artist, in collaboration with the Accademia Albertina. In May 2022, 'Sgambetto', a chess competition, was held in the garden. Special chessboards and prizes for the winners were created by Bastione's artists. Still in May, Bastione organized a project based on the artistic work of two of its members, Jacopo Mandich and Emanuele Marullo, in the form of an exhibition called '1+1 0', with artworks spread around the building and the garden. The exhibition lasted less than a month, and a concert of electronic music was organized for the finissage. The 'Panorama' event, organized a week later, is an example of an event curated by Bastione, a gathering focused on sound research and experimentation, dedicated to ambient music, field recording, and itinerant energies. It takes place at sunset on a panoramic terrace at Villa Rey, which, for the occasion, becomes a stage for sound experimentation. The idea is based on the concept of panorama, understood as a comprehensive view of the possibilities offered by the contemporary world, aiming to provide connections between local and international communities. Music, like performance, adapts to historical and social evolutions, supporting and encouraging especially younger generations who act as spokespersons for societal changes and expressive languages.

Figure 7.8 '1+1 0'. Source: Bastione archives

Still in June 2022, CREMA was inaugurated. Like '1+1 0', this exhibition extended beyond the indoor spaces of the Villa Rey and included part of the garden. Organised by Bastione, CREMA was a collective exhibition by students of the Accademia Albertina, curated by the artist and teacher Franko B. Other similar events followed, all characterised by the intention to give space to others and to create with others: in one way or another, Bastione was always present in the projects and events. And their practice was an experiment with the new space: from inside to outside, becoming more and more aware of the potential of their spaces. The event observed for this research through participant observation, was one of their most recent events. They organized a micro-festival called 'Microonde' in April 2024. This one-day event was the culmination of a month-long residency by four artist collectives invited by Bastione. During their weeks at the Villa, they were able to experiment, co-create and eat with Bastione's artists in the Villa's spaces. In the words of the artists, it was a collaborative residency where they were directly

involved in the production process of the performers: from the first days, during the shared meals, to the final event where they shared the results of the practice with the audience. Through MICROONDE, Bastione experiments with the possibility of organizing artistic residencies, hosting several artists invited to the event, offering the opportunity for site-specific projects. Bastione aims to trigger moments of interaction, allowing artists to inhabit the spaces and build relationships with them. Through moments of shared experience in the location, it fosters aggregation and socialization around a "making" process that should motivate participants to experiment with a different way of being "active."

Figure 7.9 "Swinging is like saying no no no" Marta Mangini and Nicola di Croce. Performance during MICROONDE 2023 at the main hall of Villa Rey. Source: Bastione archives

7.2.2 Space for the community

During the events at Villa Rey, the use of space and the involvement of guest artists followed the same basic principles as those established at Cavallerizza Reale. However, after a period of nomadism and forced residency, the artists of Associazione Bastione approached these practices with greater intentionality,

gradually adopting a more structured and strategic approach. The literature emphasizes the importance of space for independent art spaces, as it offers a practical detachment from the commercial pressures of the art market, thereby creating opportunities for artistic experimentation (Vorobeva, 2022; Wright 2024). At the same time, these spaces are understood as sites for collective identity formation and community building (Lim et al., 2019; Lobo, 2018; Zilberstein, 2019; Gurney, 2023). It is at this intersection of artistic autonomy and engagement with the urban context that the relationship between the art market and the urban community becomes more evident. The public engagement of independent art spaces beyond the confines of the art world has received little attention in organizational and cultural studies that rather focus on artistic production and internal organization (Blessi et al., 2011; De Giampaulis, 2021). For their part, urban studies tend to emphasize the role of these spaces as catalysts for social change and urban regeneration (Malatjie, 2013; Lim et al., 2019). Bastione's practice cannot be fully understood without integrating these different perspectives: organization, artistic creation and activation of urban regeneration processes. Their work at Villa Rey, built on a foundation of care for the space and the people who inhabit it, is an example of how space and community become central to both their artistic practice and their organizational strategy. Through this focus, Bastione promotes the creation of communities bound to a space and also establishes broader interactions with the urban context, positioning itself as both a site of artistic innovation and a contributor to urban regeneration.

In the words of the artists, the spaces in Cavallerizza played an important role in fostering a sense of community, and they continue to do so in a more attentive and conscious way in Villa Rey: "The need for space is not just about having a place to work - it is about creating a shared environment where artists can come together to co-create, collaborate and build something bigger". Also, "It's not just about having a roof over our heads to work in; it's about having a space where we can connect and create something together". This collective approach is deeply embedded in Bastione's artistic practice, where creative care extends beyond the physical renovation of spaces to include the revitalization of such spaces through

the creation of a community. Indeed, through its one-day micro-festivals (see 7.2.1), Bastione seeks to extend the relevance of the space to the hosted artists and the wider urban community. "The one-day events are a way for us to open up the space to the community, to invite people in and make them part of what we're doing," explains one artist. "These gatherings create temporary but meaningful communities where artists, neighbors and visitors come together to share food, drink and, of course, art. The informal, inclusive nature of these events fosters a sense of belonging and allows participants to actively contribute to the creative process: "It's not just about watching art happen, it's about being part of it. In this way, the space serves as a platform for co-creation, where the boundaries between artist and audience blur and the act of making art becomes a shared experience.

Bastione's artists point out that these participatory practices are not new, but they are revolutionary in our times, when the market seems to dominate every aspect of our lives, including art: "We're not reinventing the wheel, we're building on something much older. Just as the Dadaist performances at the Cabaret Voltaire invited audience participation, Bastione's micro-festivals blur the lines between creator and audience, encouraging interaction and engagement". Of course, Bastione's practice is not like these performances, but rather rooted in care and connection, reflecting a more contemporary understanding of participation in the arts: "It's about creating a space where people feel connected, where they can engage with art and each other in a meaningful way".

7.2.3 Audience or community?

Museum formats and boundaries have been challenged since the 50s in the evolving dynamics of contemporary art, with contemporary media such as street art emerging as a dynamic form of expression that challenges norms and engages audiences in unconventional ways (Blanché, 2015; Costa and Lopes, 2015). Also, new museum formats that take exhibitions to the peripheries of cities and engage new communities, such as MoCa in Los Angeles, are emerging. Literature also highlights how artist-led, independent practices have become informal places for artists working outside of conventional institutions, fostering community

engagement and artistic experimentation (Blessi et al., 2011; Malatjie, 2013). The evolving dynamic shows how the boundaries of conventional structures such as museums and galleries have been challenged in recent decades, while always maintaining a line between production and realization. Instead, Bastione's practice is an example of how the boundaries between production and access to art are indeed beginning to blur through a reshaping of the dynamics of production, with the audience becoming an integral part of the artistic process. Looking at the story of Bastione was useful to see how the practice of audience engagement becomes a spontaneous act of community development that emerges and evolves over time. Bastione's first exhibition project at the Bastione San Maurizio in Cavallerizza, 'Apotema', explored the relationship between movement and space: "It was a shift from just showing art to creating an environment where the space and the people involved became part of the art". This project marked a starting point for their practice where the act of making art became a practice of co-creation, with the artists, the audience and the space becoming integral to the creative process. Rather than simply observing, the audience was invited to engage and become part of the practice: "It wasn't just about putting something on display, it was about inviting people in and making them part of the whole story". This approach was also evident in 'AFFITTASI' in opening up their space at the bastion to hosted artists and collectives, as well as residents and citizen, and transforming it into a collaborative artistic hub: "It was a space where everyone, whether they were artists or not, could contribute," said one member. The lines between artists and audience began to blur as more people - artists and non-artists - became involved in shaping the space: "It was about breaking down the barrier between who's making the art and who's experiencing it."

7.2.4 Hospitality and co-creation

The first event at Villa Rey, the one-day festival 'Se non tocchi, non cade', was a celebration of both artistic experimentation and community creation. The audience was invited to interact with the artworks, mainly piñatas - sculptures that could be broken open to reveal hidden contents - transforming the audience into

active participants in the artistic process. The concept of participation was further explored in the one-day micro-festival 'Microonde' (2024), an opportunity for Bastione to develop and reflect on the concepts of hospitality and co-creation. The idea of creating a community as part of their artistic practice itself arose while conceiving this performance-based event. The conception and development of the residency, and then its restitution during the micro-festival, brought together different groups: the artists of Bastione, the hosted artists and the audience. Figure 7.10 gives a visual representation of how the artists of Bastione conceived the community that was created through artistic practice. Microonde began with the idea of using the spaces inside and outside Villa Rey to host the production and dissemination of artists' performances. It was therefore the group of artists of the Bastione, a small 'self-managed artistic community', that opened itself up to welcome another community of guest artists to expand its own and give life to a new community, an 'extended artistic community'. The process of artistic creation was thus structured and took place over the weeks of the residency, during which the invited artists experimented with the space and the self-managed artistic community (i.e. the 10 artists of Bastione). It was only on the day of the micro-festival that the extended artistic community expanded to include the audience, and it was only at that moment that the artistic creation was complete, once contact with the third component of the community (the audience) had taken place. Indeed, the artistic creation of the four invited collectives themselves presupposed the presence of the community of visitors, the so-called "audience community", through performances that involved all the senses (e.g. with performers touching the audience in a dark room and offering them hot tea). As shown in Figure 7.7 the audience community includes not only the visitors, but also the artists of Bastione, as well as the members of the invited collectives. Artistic creation thus becomes not only site-specific, but also 'community-specific', based on the participation of the whole community. The event served to build a conscious process where the distinction between artist and audience blurred, as the artistic practice was inherently linked to the interactions between these different groups.

Figure 7.10 Creating a community as an artistic practice: the case of Associazione Bastione. Source: author's own elaboration.

Bastione's practice challenges traditional notions of audience's participation in museums (Simon, 2010), suggesting that the act of witnessing art is not enough to define one as part of the audience. In her model, the audience becomes an active element of the artwork itself, enhancing co-creation (Dekker and Morea, 2023). This practice redefines the concept of 'audience' to include a broader understanding of participation that includes creation, collaboration and dialogue. Bastione's evolution from being open to the community of Cavallerizza to actively and consciously building a community illustrates an artistic and organizational practice in which the boundaries between production, dissemination and realization are

increasingly blurred. "We have never perceived the audience as passive observers," said one artist, emphasizing that the group's projects are not just exhibitions, but living processes that actively engage with their context and the people within it. This approach challenges the standard notion of the audience as external to the artistic process: "From the beginning it was clear that the people who came into contact with our work were as much a part of it as the artists themselves," explained another member, positioning the audience as an integral part of the work itself. In this sense, the 'audience' becomes indistinguishable from the 'community'. "It is hard to separate who is an artist and who is a member of the audience, because everyone plays a role in shaping what the art becomes," argued one artist. Those who interact with art are not spectators, but participants in the creation of meaning. The community of artists and visitors plays a central role in the artistic process and directly influences the outcome of the work. "The space and the people in it both contribute to the final work. It's not something we control alone". It is because everyone plays a role in shaping what art becomes that this concept is strongly present during the first public opening on the inauguration day of Associazione Bastione. The decision to create piñata-sculptures and have them destroyed by the public represents a symbolic and collective act with multiple meanings. Piñatas, traditionally associated with play, celebration, and moments of breaking, are objects that invite active participation and emotional involvement. Their destruction is not just a playful gesture, but also becomes a metaphor for transformation: breaking to create and open new beginnings. In this context, the destruction of the piñata-sculptures by the public makes tangible the idea of a fusion between the creator and the consumer of art. The audience becomes a direct protagonist of the performative act and the work itself, contributing with their gesture to the creation of a shared meaning. This approach highlights how art is no longer a passive experience, but a collective act that puts the artist and the community into dialogue.

7.3 Maintaining artistic autonomy, seeking dialogue with the government and facing institutional voids

7.3.1 The formal practice at Villa Rey and the premises for its organizational evolution

Following their eviction, the group's transition to a more nomadic practice raised the need for formalisation: it became clear to the artists that establishing a formal structure was crucial to ensuring the sustainability and visibility of their practice. In fact, the transition from informality to association has been a gradual and demanding process, requiring considerable time, energy and commitment from members. In the years since the eviction, all the artists have graduated and concluded their student phase, taking on professional commitments and new priorities. This development has led to a recalibration of roles within the group, with the result that the practice is "no longer a full-time commitment for everyone. At the same time, however, the aims of the practice have matured and their artistic practice is now approached with a more structured and long-term perspective.

As far as space is concerned, their practice in Villa Rey is organized so as to be within the limits set by the City Council through the concession. However, they are trying to extend the boundaries of this concession to include the green space of the garden. As one artist said: "We would like to create a public art park in the garden, but it is often difficult to move forward with such projects due to bureaucracy and the challenges of obtaining the necessary permits, as the government is unwilling to engage in dialogue with us." In terms of community development, the group has refocused its efforts on cultivating relationships with the surrounding neighborhood, seeing community engagement as a necessary first step to having a broader impact on the city. In addition, the group is seeking to expand their concession within the building to provide more space for artist residencies, further embedding their project within the local artistic ecosystem. In these efforts, the care of the space and community development are deeply intertwined and become central organizational goals alongside artistic practices. At the same time, the group is assessing its position within the local funding system, with a particular focus on

building relationships with private foundations and securing local funding. As one member noted, 'Financially it has become impossible to sustain the events. We are expanding, but our income remains the same. And we can no longer give out of pocket'. This growing financial burden underlines the need to reposition Bastione to ensure that its artistic and social objectives remain in line with local cultural policy and funding guidelines.

7.3.2 Independence and autonomy

"For me, the question of independent space is a bit of a label that we try to fit too much into. Instead, it would be enough to analyze the differences rather than the similarities in this sense," said one artist when asked if he would define their space as independent. The focus here is on the attempts to define independent art spaces (Vorobeva 2022): "A definition that demands independence does not encourage people to create autonomy, which should be the desired outcome of artists working beyond the market". The current process of Bastione's organizational development indeed begins with the redefinition of its current practice, which takes different forms and meanings at Villa Rey and as a non-profit organization. This re-organization and internal development has required the members to rethink their role in relation to the institutions: they can no longer be defined by their practice as inoccupants. Accordingly, the definition of independence is particularly problematic when it comes to issues of funding and long-term sustainability. The literature acknowledges that independent art spaces are not self-sufficient and therefore not financially independent, as they conduct their own fundraising activities, seek private partners and sponsors, and apply for public funding, both on a regular, periodic basis and for specific projects (Blessi et al., 2011; Arthurs, 2012; Yıldız, 2020). Indeed, independent spaces often seek different forms of financial support for the operation and development of their projects. However, this creates a paradox: the search for funding often places these spaces in a state of dependency on local calls and grants. Interviews and observations at Bastione revealed that self-funding alone soon proved insufficient. As one artist recalled: "In the beginning we all contributed from our personal

savings to cover the costs, but it soon became clear that this wasn't a sustainable solution. It may have worked for the informal activity in Cavallerizza, but it became unsustainable with the costs and obligations of setting up the association. Once we started to formalize and try to get more serious about long-term planning, it was clear that we needed external funding".

The case of Bastione is particularly relevant to this issue because they have not yet received any local funding. They have part of the concession of a public building, Villa Rey, but they pay for it themselves. They sustain all the costs autonomously to continue their work and projects within that space, maintaining their independence and self-sufficiency. Interestingly, the new space actually poses some challenges for the possibility of funding. The first thing they notice is the difference with their experience in Cavallerizza, where they were literally independent and the economy was characterized by informal rules. There, Bastione was located in a cluster of occupations in Cavallerizza, where parties and exhibitions were organized with the other artists and inoccupants: "At the time, it felt like we were part of a larger ecosystem where we could share resources and support each other. It helped keep things going for a while," said one member. There was a kind of economy of scale that worked as a sustainable strategy for all the inoccupants. Unfortunately, it was a fragile economy because eviction was always around the corner, so there was no long-term strategy". A second element affecting Villa Rey's income in its current location is its physical isolation. "Being in Cavallerizza meant that there was always a flow of people, just passers-by who might drop in, or people who were already there for other events. In Villa Rey, we're outside the city center and it's harder to get that kind of spontaneous foot traffic". This change in location has reduced opportunities for interaction with the wider public, making it more difficult to generate income from events and exhibitions, and to apply for funding that prioritizes the accessibility of the space.

For these reasons, Bastione decided to adopt a strategy of sustainability considering grants and applying for an international call during the participant observation period: "We quickly realized that if we wanted to continue, we'd have

to start applying for grants and funding opportunities," said one artist. However, this period of participation showed that these funds are not always easy to come by: "Private foundations, especially those linked to banks, often require non-profits to have a formal legal structure and years of experience," explained one member, noting how this puts informal or loosely organized groups at a disadvantage. Many private foundations, such as those linked to banks in Italy, focus on supporting non-profit organizations with formal legal status and a certified history. This institutionalization of the funding process poses additional challenges for independent spaces, which may see formalization as a compromise to their original values of flexibility and experimentation: "We don't want to become too institutionalized, but we also have to survive. It is a difficult balance". In addition, public funding mechanisms are structured to require careful project planning and reporting, which some artists find intrusive in the creative process: "We found that sometimes the bureaucracy of these grants actually got in the way of the work we wanted to do. It felt like we were spending more time on paperwork than on art."

Organizational issues along these lines have been discussed in the literature, namely that artists in these spaces are seen to focus primarily on artistic production and dissemination, with little engagement with the public or stakeholders outside the cultural sector (Blessi et al., 2011; Byrne et al., 2006). However, evidence from interviews and observations suggests that the problem is the rigidity of subsidies, especially local and national ones, for these specific cases: "International funding is a bit more flexible, but the local and national calls are incredibly narrow, making it difficult for us to adapt our projects," argued one artist. While these funding mechanisms may work for more established institutions, they prove ineffective for experimental and informal practices such as those found at Bastione.

7.3.3 Urban dialogues

In addition to seeking funding for artistic activities and internal organization, Bastione has sought to engage in dialogue with the local government about the management and revitalization of the spaces at Villa Rey. When the group began its informal practice in Cavallerizza Reale in 2017, the building was in a state of

neglect. As one member recalls, "The space was in a state of neglect, but it had so much potential. We wanted to bring it back to life, not only through art, but also by making it a place for people to meet". Their efforts went beyond artistic creation, as they sought to make the space a community hub through a range of activities, including installations, performances and workshops. These events not only contributed to the restoration of the building, but also brought together local residents and visitors, fostering a holistic process of urban regeneration. A key aspect of this revitalization process has been the involvement of artists in the maintenance and care of outdoor spaces. At Cavallerizza, for example, they played an active role in maintaining the gardens, incorporating sustainable practices such as mowing the grass and cultivating plants. This commitment to caring for the space continued after their eviction from Cavallerizza, as they continued similar efforts at Villa Rey. At their new location, they created a dyeing garden, demonstrating their continued commitment to extend their practices of care to surrounding green areas.

However, despite their legally recognized presence at Villa Rey, the artists have faced significant challenges in their efforts to maintain and use the space, particularly concerning the garden. While the artists have a concession for the building itself, the garden is maintained by Verde di Torino, which cuts the grass and takes care of the park. It is not in a state of total neglect, but some areas of the garden, such as the main entrance, require restoration, which is currently hindered by the lack of funding. This situation remains a significant obstacle to Associazione Bastione's broader goal of transforming the space into a public art park. Although some members of the collective would like to create such a park within the garden in the future, no formal procedure has been initiated yet. This remains a difficult path, as obtaining permits from local authorities is often a challenging and slow process. Their ability to fully realize their vision is constrained by the limitations of their concession and the lack of government support for their plans. They must respect the boundaries of the concession, as additional activities require permits, and the garden areas are managed by different entities.

Figure 7.11 The area granted to Villa dell'Arte, to which Associazione Bastione is affiliated in order to use the spaces for carrying out artistic activities⁹. Source: Associazione Bastione' archive.

The nature of Bastione's practices is crucial in contributing to discourses on the care of shared spaces in the urban context (Williams, 2017). As one artist noted, 'it's not just about occupying space for art's sake - it's about a genuine interest in making these spaces open and accessible to everyone'. This statement particularly resonates with the literature on urban occupations and *centri sociali* in the Italian context, which highlights the role of grassroots movements in reclaiming urban spaces as sites of public use, rather than allowing them to be dominated by market forces or government neglect (Borchi, 2018; Borchi, 2020; Lenna et al., 2020). In this context, Bastione's efforts can be seen as part of a wider struggle for urban commons – shared spaces that are collectively managed and maintained by the community.

7.3.4 The transition to formalisation

⁹ The map on the left shows the entire Villa, with the section of the Bastione highlighted in yellow. Other areas are marked as belonging to the Villa dell'Arte and the ASI. On the map to the right, the section of the Bastione is highlighted in yellow, while the letter A marks the part of the park (including the terrace) shared by Villa dell'Arte, ASI and the Bastione (the area used by the Bastione for events). The areas marked B, C, D, E and H are the responsibility of the local government.

Rather than improving Bastione's financial stability, the transition to formalizations has introduced additional bureaucracy and organizational challenges. As one artist noted, "The transition has not only led to higher operating costs, but has also changed the dynamics of the group. The once fluid and collaborative nature of our previous environment at Cavallerizza has given way to a more formalized and constrained atmosphere at Villa Rey". "The spectrum of costs and benefits associated with this transition ranges from the economic to the emotional", as one artist pointed out; "That's a pretty wide range, isn't it?". A tangible benefit shared by the collective is their access to the villa, made possible by the concession, facilitated by the social capital of artists that made possible to continue the mission of Villa dell'Arte. Villa dell'Arte had begun to lose momentum and needed transformation, which was realized through its absorption of Bastione. This shift allowed Bastione to become the new focal point of Villa dell'Arte's mission. The organization saved a historic space by winning the grant, and the affiliation with Bastione signifies a renewal of its mission—from conservation to the promotion and enhancement of emerging art. This tangible advantage is complemented by intangible benefits such as "the opportunity to work together, share ideas and resources, and build a sense of community". However, these benefits are associated with challenges similar to those experienced within families, in particular the difficulty of reconciling different perspectives and career paths. Bastione's constant challenge is to maintain cohesion in the midst of these differences and to keep the common vision that originated in Cavallerizza. Indeed, divergent aspirations within the group also contribute to its current instability. While some members focus on sustaining their artistic practices and seeking external financial opportunities, others prioritize their role within the collective. This tension between individual ambitions and collective responsibilities creates a complex environment of financial and emotional challenges. In general, the transition to a more formalized structure has necessitated increased bureaucracy, which many feel has detracted from the spontaneous and creative flow that the artists once benefited from.

On top of these challenges comes the challenge of funding and budget management. The organization primarily relies on the voluntary work of its founding members, who contribute their time and expertise without compensation. Each year, a sum is allocated in advance to cover the operational costs of the association. Team members provide their own equipment and materials to support activities, and some external volunteers often assist with projects during public-facing events to manage and welcome visitors. The association has also received donations to support projects in collaboration with external entities. These methods allow the association to maintain an active schedule of initiatives despite limited financial resources. The association is committed to minimizing underpaid work, recognizing the value of the contribution made by artists and staff involved. However, given the non-profit nature of the organization and limited financial resources, there are situations where work is compensated below its actual value, and it is possible that guest artists may not receive fees, but only travel reimbursements or support for production costs. The organization tries to balance this limitation by offering hospitality, technical support, other forms of assistance, and non-monetary benefits such as shared meals, where friends of the group are invited and each guest brings a dish to share, creating a festive, communal atmosphere. Opportunities for exposure, training, and professional development are also provided. This includes a constant commitment by the team to ensure hospitality, preparation and optimization of exhibition spaces, retrieval of necessary equipment, and everything required to ensure a successful event.

The organization is actively working to find additional funding and resources to improve working conditions, ensure fairer compensation for all those contributing to its activities, and to continually enrich the offerings provided to the community. Looking to the future, Bastione hopes to adopt a sustainable economic model that includes fees for invited artists and financial returns for the team and external collaborators. This change would enable the attraction and retention of high-quality professionals, improve the organization of the team, build local-level projects, and ensure sustainable and long-lasting growth, while appropriately valuing the work of all participants.

Chapter 8

Discussion

This chapter draws together the findings from the empirical analysis and engages them with the theoretical framework developed in the earlier chapters, particularly the VBA. It aims to situate Associazione Bastione's practices within broader debates about cultural value, market dynamics and the changing dynamics of cultural production in the urban context. Bastione's practices, situated in the post-industrial context of Turin, reflect the tradition of socially engaged art as explained in chapter 1 and align with the *zeitgeist*. The VBA framework allows for an articulation of the multiple value dimensions of the contemporary. It helps make sense of how Bastione creates transcendental and social value through experimental and collaborative practices; how it sustains personal and oikos values through informal relations, care, and shared responsibility; and how it engages with the market and public sector without being fully subordinated to either. This multidimensional understanding is crucial to analyzing what makes Bastione's model both typical of broader shifts in artistic labor and distinct in its particular configuration. In this sense, through the analysis, Bastione's position within the civil sphere becomes clearer. The artists involved in Bastione operate as civic agents, contributing to the common good through cultural practice. Their work resonates with Klamer's (2017) argument that cultural production should be understood beyond economic and policy terms, as embedded in broader social relationships that span the market, the public sector, and the *oikos*. Thus, this chapter shows how Associazione Bastione exemplifies a hybrid model of cultural production that negotiates independence, community engagement, and institutional cooperation. It offers a framework for rethinking the role of artists today.

8.1 How the VBA helps answer the research questions

The central research question—How do independent art spaces reshape the boundaries between the market, the public sector, and the civil sphere in contemporary cultural production?—was explored through the interpretative lens provided by the VBA. The empirical study, based on interviews, participant observation, and close attention to organizational and artistic practices, revealed how the group's trajectory—from occupation to formalizations—was shaped by a negotiation between artistic autonomy, urban embeddedness, and institutional engagement. This directly addresses the second and third sub-questions of the thesis: *In what ways do independent art spaces organize cultural production through collective use, co-creation, and situated governance?* and *How do these practices generate and negotiate value(s) that escape conventional economic or policy-driven evaluative frameworks?*

Figure 8.1 synthesizes the findings of this analysis by mapping the entanglement of Bastione's practice across the five spheres of value: market, government, social, personal, and transcendental. In the market sphere, Bastione developed an autonomous infrastructure through event-making, artistic residencies, and temporary collaborations—strategically interacting with the market while maintaining autonomy. Their work shows how informal art spaces selectively enter the market to sustain themselves, often redefining artistic careers in the process. This corresponds with the sub-theme "Redefining the way artists make art, network and build careers", highlighting a shift toward self-determined visibility and hybrid professional trajectories.

In the government sphere, the group's engagement with public institutions became increasingly strategic following their eviction. The transition to Villa Rey triggered a more formal dialogue with local authorities and foundations, aiming to secure stability and recognition. Yet, these efforts also encountered bureaucratic voids and institutional friction—particularly in the management of urban commons like the Villa Rey garden. This tension reflects the broader contextual constraints explored in the fourth sub-question: *What contextual conditions (urban, social, political) enable or constrain these alternative modes of cultural production?*

The social sphere, at the heart of Bastione's identity, manifests through co-creation, hospitality, and care. The micro-festivals and participatory installations demonstrate how their artistic work is inseparable from their community-building efforts. Here, artistic value is deeply relational and grounded in shared experiences—a civic commitment often neglected in conventional evaluations but essential to understanding the broader significance of grassroots cultural initiatives.

On the personal level, Bastione's horizontal organization and fluid authorship reflect the individual aspirations of its members and their refusal to conform to traditional career paths. Their autonomy is framed as an affirmative project rooted in mutual responsibility and care for the collective. The tension between personal ambition and collective needs, especially in a self-managed structure, reveals how artistic labor is also shaped by affective and ethical considerations.

Finally, the transcendental sphere emerges in Bastione's poetic reimagining of space—transforming abandoned sites into spaces of shared imagination and meaning. Their attention to symbolic gestures, community rituals, and ecological awareness reflects a commitment to ideals that transcend immediate functionality. Initiatives like the dyeing garden or the transformation of Villa Rey into an art park underscore how independent art spaces articulate values that are civic, aesthetic, and ethical all at once.

8.2 Visualization of the findings: A value trail

Together, the dimensions illustrated in 8.1 offer a situated understanding of how Bastione's practice addresses and redefines the boundaries between market, state, and civil society. The diagram could form the basis of future analyses of independent art spaces. Through the articulation of the values underpinning Bastione's practice in the five spheres of the value-based approach—market, government, social, personal, and transcendental—the figure makes visible the relational and hybrid nature of grassroots artistic work. It enables an understanding of how different dimensions of value co-exist, overlap, and occasionally come into tension within independent initiatives. This model may therefore serve as a heuristic tool for further research, allowing for the comparison of situated practices across

diverse contexts. It provides a structured yet flexible framework to map how independent art spaces negotiate artistic autonomy, institutional relationships, and civic engagement, while foregrounding values that are often neglected in conventional cultural policy or market-based analysis.

On the left-hand side ('Stating the facts'), the diagram shows how Bastione has shaped its artistic practice through specific organizational dynamics, being unstructured in the years at Bastione San Maurizio and reaching a more mature state at Villa Rey. The three macro-themes are broken down here into the main sub-themes that emerged from the analysis. The different shapes indicate the values of the value-based approach (social, societal, personal, transcendental) that inform each micro-theme, while the arrows indicate their chronological progression. On the right-hand side ('Map of Values'), the square illustrates Bastione's vision for the future, highlighting its growing awareness of the values associated with its practices and the associated vision. These include the growing desire to expand their infrastructure to broaden their artistic practice, the intention to turn their informal organization into a strategic resource to become more structured and strategic, the transition from an informal group to a formal association and the challenges this brings, the aim to secure financial sustainability through increased visibility, the need to expand their current social impact into a societal one.

Figure 8.1. The dynamics of Associazione Bastione's value trail: Creative conversations between artists, the market, urban communities and institutions.

Source: author's own elaboration.

8.3 Contributions and societal impact of the research

The aim of this research was to develop a broader understanding of value creation in independent art spaces, with particular attention to their embeddedness in specific socio-urban conditions and their relationship to the art market. Through a combination of deductive and inductive methods, the study drew on an in-depth case study of Associazione Bastione to examine how independent art spaces contribute to contemporary art ecosystems and to civil society. The interview guide was informed by findings from the literature and contextual knowledge, while the open-ended analysis of interviews allowed for emergent insights to surface, shaping a grounded and multidimensional understanding of the field.

The study's primary contribution lies in the application of the Value-Based Approach (VBA) to the analysis of independent art spaces. This framework enabled a thorough examination of how spaces like Associazione Bastione generate multiple, intersecting forms of value. Crucially, the VBA proved effective in tracing how these initiatives operate across, and in relation to, the market, public institutions, and civil society. The extensive literature on independent art spaces and grassroots artistic practices suggests that these spaces operate across multiple dimensions. However, this literature rarely accounts for the full range of spheres in which this horizontality is expressed. The VBA instead offers a coherent framework for capturing this complexity, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of how independent art spaces negotiate and redefine their roles within contemporary urban and cultural ecosystems.

The “value trail” model developed in this study offers a conceptual synthesis of these findings. It outlines three key domains of value creation:

1. Redefining artistic practices (creation, formats, careers);
2. Caring for space and building communities (hospitality, co-creation, shared use of space);

3. Maintaining autonomy while cultivating institutional dialogue (urban dialogue, sustainability, care).

The aim is to provide an analytical tool for future research on independent art spaces and support comparative investigations across different urban and institutional contexts. Importantly, the study also contributes to cultural policy debates identifying challenges faced by independent spaces i.e. financial precarity, institutional misalignment and the lack of long-term support infrastructures. At the same time, it highlights the societal potential of these initiatives to act as mediators between artists, communities and institutions. Bastione's strategic yet autonomous approach—rooted in values of hospitality, mutualism, and collective care—demonstrates how independent art spaces can move beyond oppositional stances to model alternative forms of governance, relationship with the market and public engagement, acting within the civil society.

Ultimately, this research encourages a reorientation in how independent art spaces are understood and supported. Instead of viewing them as marginal or temporary actors operating at the lower end of the market, or as instrumental actors of urban regeneration, they should be recognized as integral members of civil society. They are capable of meaningfully contributing to urban regeneration, cultural innovation, and the use of commons.

Conclusion

Artists are not world-changers: they are part of civil society

This research has explored the dynamics of independent art spaces through an in-depth case study of Associazione Bastione, focusing on how such practices reshape boundaries between the market, the public sector, and the civil sphere. The study's central contribution lies in its application of the Value-Based Approach (VBA), which enabled a multidimensional understanding of Bastione's artistic and organizational practices, as well as their broader civic role.

One of the key insights emerging from this work is that the absence of a universally accepted definition of "independent art space" should not be considered a limitation. On the contrary, this conceptual ambiguity enables a more nuanced understanding of practices that challenge rigid institutional classifications. The flexibility of the term reflects the adaptive and situated nature of these spaces as they respond to urban, social, and political conditions.

Through an abductive research process that combined theoretical frameworks with grounded fieldwork, the study has shown that Associazione Bastione's value creation is not reducible to symbolic or economic dimensions alone. Instead, it extends to social, personal, societal, and transcendental realms. This multi-layered value structure mirrors both the lived experiences of the artists and the relational dynamics that underpin their practice. As such, this thesis has also been shaped by the researcher's own positionality, recognizing that the initial engagement with Bastione was driven by many of the same values later identified through empirical analysis—care, commitment, and a desire for collective agency.

The analysis further reveals that Bastione's trajectory shares commonalities with many grassroots artistic initiatives—such as reclaiming disused urban spaces,

fostering community engagement, and prioritizing artistic autonomy—but also stands apart in several key respects. While many similar initiatives tend to resist formalizations or remain loosely organized, Bastione has undertaken a sustained and strategic process of engagement with institutional actors without sacrificing its horizontal structure or creative independence. Their initial actions at Bastione San Maurizio resembled other grassroots collectives in their spontaneous and informal use of space. However, their later move to Villa Rey, and the accompanying effort to develop infrastructures, secure funding, and establish constructive relations with local authorities, mark a more deliberate hybridization. This dual orientation—remaining rooted in collective artistic values while actively seeking dialogue with the public sector—highlights Bastione’s specific position within the broader field of independent cultural production.

This research contributes to current debates on artistic labor, commons-based cultural production, and the institutionalization of socially engaged art practices. It suggests that Bastione’s hybrid identity—as both artistic collective and civic actor—enables it to model alternative forms of governance, value creation, and public engagement. Practices such as hospitality, co-creation, and participatory events have redefined the relationship between artists and audiences, challenging the top-down logic of traditional institutions.

Moreover, the association’s engagement with local authorities and foundations, while maintaining artistic autonomy, reveals the potential for independent art spaces to participate in civil society in meaningful ways. Their negotiation of urban space, search for sustainability, and cultivation of community-oriented practices reflect a broader shift in the role of artists—from market actors to agents within the civil sphere. This resonates with Klamer’s (2017) typology of societal spheres and affirms the relevance of the civil perspective in analyzing contemporary artistic labor.

The concept of care, introduced in the final chapter and synthesized through the visual model, underscores the affective and ethical dimensions of Bastione’s work. It illustrates how care for space, people, and processes is central to their practice, and how this ethic supports both resilience and innovation. This framework invites

further inquiry into the interplay between autonomy, community, and public value in the arts.

In conclusion, this thesis argues for a reorientation of how independent art spaces are understood and supported. Rather than romanticizing autonomy or resisting all forms of institutional engagement, these initiatives construct new ecologies of value that challenge established norms and invite institutional reflection. Future research should continue to explore the tensions and synergies between independence, governance, and cultural policy, attending to the values that guide practice and the contextual conditions that shape them. It is critical to start rethink independent art spaces such as Bastione as not marginal or anomalous but rather incorporated in the practices of civil society.

Glossary

This section presents an analysis of the key terms used in this dissertation from a semantic perspective. Throughout the research process, at seminars and presentations, as well as during the drafting of the dissertation, some terms were used. In particular, those terms that are more problematic in their definition, including the concept of contemporary art itself, were identified as requiring further examination.

Audience

NOUN

- The term "spectators" or "listeners" is used to describe the individuals present at a public event, such as a theatrical performance, a movie, a musical concert.
- The collective of individuals who engage with a given text, whether in the form of a written work, an audio recording, or a visual presentation, particularly those who are the intended audience of an artist or a performer.
- In the field of cultural studies, the term is used to describe the broader public that engages with cultural products. In the last decades this engagement is not seen as merely passive consumption anymore; rather, it encompasses active interpretation of the cultural content in question and participation (Simon, 2010).

This dissertation examines the concept of the audience in the context of independent art spaces, where the traditional passive role of the audience is often redefined. Independent spaces typically facilitate more participatory and interactive forms of engagement, wherein the audience assumes a role in the creative process or communal activities. The shift challenges the conventional relationship between

artist and viewer, fostering a more profound connection and collaborative engagement within cultural spaces. In such settings, the audience is frequently more closely aligned with the local urban community, thereby reinforcing the social value of art.

Contemporary Art

NOUN

- Contemporary art is defined as art produced in current times, often reflecting current issues, ideas, and the *zeitgeist*. The term is typically used to refer to art created from the late 20th century to the present day (Poli, 2015).
- Contemporary art is characterized by a diversity of media, styles and themes and it frequently prioritizes ideas over images.

The term is particularly multilayered in this research because it is not bound by specific techniques or media. Rather, it is defined by its relation to the prevailing cultural discourse and its capacity to reflect and challenge the structures of contemporary society, consistently aligning itself with the *zeitgeist*. Independent art spaces provide an optimal environment for the development of contemporary art, as they often foster experimentation and processes that transcend the commercial pressures of the traditional art market and align with the *zeitgeist*.

Culture

NOUN

- The collective term for the arts and other manifestations of human intellectual achievement.
- The set of shared values, beliefs, and practices that define a community and its identity (Klamer, 2017).

This dissertation conceptualises culture as a comprehensive and dynamic context that influences the behaviours, values and practices of individuals and groups. It plays a relevant role in the creation of independent art spaces, where informal relationships and collective cultural production offer an alternative to market-driven art practices. Furthermore, the dissertation makes reference to the anthropological concept of culture, which is understood as an ongoing process of meaning-making that is continuously shaped by the interactions within the social fabric.

Independent

ADJECTIVE

- Free from external control or influence, particularly from established institutions, markets or government agencies

In this dissertation, the term "independent" refers to art spaces that are artist-led and operate at the margins of institutional art worlds and urban governance structures. These spaces typically function outside formalized systems of funding, recognition, or evaluation. Rather than being solely defined by their non-affiliation with commercial galleries or public institutions, their independence lies in their capacity to generate autonomous and situated practices. They priorities artistic experimentation, spatial reappropriation, and collective governance. As such, they blur the boundaries between artistic labor, civic action, and community building. Independence, therefore, is conceived as a dynamic and context-specific condition—emerging from the artists' responses to local socio-spatial constraints and opportunities, while maintaining a commitment to non-instrumental, relational, and collaborative forms of cultural production.

Market

NOUN

- The term is used to describe a system or arena in which goods, services, or cultural products are exchanged, often governed by the dynamics of supply and demand, pricing mechanisms, and consumer choice. In the cultural field, the market typically refers to institutions, networks, and intermediaries that facilitate the circulation and commodification of artistic work.
- Markets are not neutral spaces: they reflect specific power structures, value regimes, and gatekeeping mechanisms. In the cultural sector, the market often privileges visibility, branding, and commercial viability over alternative or community-based forms of value production.

This dissertation argues that an understanding of the role of independent art spaces is contingent upon a critical engagement with the concept of market. While these spaces often operate outside or at the margins of formal art markets, they remain entangled with its logics, facing issues of visibility, funding, and sustainability. Independent spaces challenge market-based norms cultivating alternative value systems rooted in collective use, contextual relevance, and community agency. As such, they offer a vantage point from which to interrogate the market's influence on cultural production and to imagine more plural and value-based economies of art.

Urban community

NOUN

- The term is used to describe a group of people who live and interact within a city. These individuals are characterized by shared social, economic, and cultural ties, which contribute to the formation of a distinct urban community.
- Urban communities frequently mirror the diversity of the city itself, encompassing a multitude of demographics, professions, and subcultures.

- In urban studies, the concept places emphasis on the networks of relationships, communal activities and shared spaces.

This dissertation argues that an understanding of the role of independent art spaces is contingent upon an appreciation of the concept of urban community. Such spaces frequently engage with and reflect the needs and aspirations of local urban contexts and people, thereby creating opportunities for cultural participation that extend beyond the scope of traditional art institutions. Independent spaces facilitate social cohesion, foster dialogue, and promote community-driven cultural production, thereby reinforcing the interconnection between art and the urban context.

Urban context

NOUN

- The physical, social, and economic environment of a city or town encompasses a multitude of factors, including the built structures, streets, public spaces, and social dynamics that shape the urban fabric.
- It denotes the interrelationship between human activities, social behaviors and the physical configuration of urban areas.

In this research, the term is used to describe the broader environment in which independent art spaces operate. Particular attention is paid to the ways in which these spaces interact with the city's infrastructure, communities and local economies. It is of great importance to understand the relationship between urban spaces and independent art spaces, as this will enable to appreciate how art can contribute to urban regeneration, community building, and alternative forms of cultural production. Independent spaces frequently emerge in urban areas that have been overlooked by commercial development, thereby creating novel dynamics of space, community, and cultural expression.

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